

**SCHOOL AND STUDENTS' FACTORS AS PREDICTORS OF SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN
PHYSICS IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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ABSTRACT

It appears there is a decline in the performance of secondary school students in physics in the past years. The study investigated the influence of school and students' factors as predictors of students' performance in secondary school physics.

The study employed an ex-post facto research design of survey research method. Simple random sampling was used to select four local government areas from the sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State. Simple random sampling was also used to select twelve (12) schools from the four local government areas. One physics teacher was randomly selected from each of the twelve schools used. The physics students were selected at random at the discretion of the physics teacher in each of the schools. A total of four hundred and fifty (450) students were used for this study, making it a total of four hundred and sixty-two (462) participants. Five instruments were used to gather information from the respondents which are; Students' Parental Influence Questionnaire (SPIQ), School Environment Questionnaire (SEQ), Physics Instructional Materials Checklist (PIMC), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and Physics Achievement Test (PAT) with reliability coefficients of 0.74, 0.68, 0.65, 0.82 and 0.94 respectively.

Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis. The result reveals that four of the school and students' factors (availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification, background in mathematics and parental socioeconomic status) have a positive influence on students' performance in physics while the remaining two factors (school environment and parental motivation) have negative correlation on students' performance in physics. Also, the result revealed that students' background in mathematics significantly predicts students' academic performance in physics.

The study concluded that physics teachers should endeavour to teach prerequisite mathematics concepts in physics before engaging them in real physics teaching as this will allow for meaningful understanding and integration of mathematics concepts embedded in physics contents.

Key Words: School Factors, Students' Factors, Academic Performance in Physics

Word Count: 308

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Olukayode Emmanuel APATA carried out this study under my supervision at the International Centre for Educational Evaluation (ICEE), Institute of Education, University of Ibadan.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to God Almighty my creator, my source of inspiration, wisdom, knowledge and understanding. He has been the source of my strength throughout this program and on His wings only have I soared.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page.....	i
Abstract.....	ii
Certification.....	iii
Dedication.....	iv
Acknowledgement.....	v
Table of Contents.....	vi
List of Tables.....	ix

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study.....	1
Statement of the Problem.....	14
Research Questions.....	14
Scope of the Study.....	15
Significance of the Study.....	15
Operational Definition of Terms.....	15
Acronyms and Abbreviation.....	16

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction.....	18
Theoretical Background.....	18
Skinnerian Environmental Theory.....	19
Constructivism Learning Theory.....	20
Concept of School Related Factors and Teaching-learning Process.....	24
School Environment as Determinants of Students Academic Performance.....	25

Instructional Materials and Students' Academic Performance.....	28
Teachers' Qualification and Students' Academic Performance in Physics.....	31
Influence of Background Knowledge on Students' Acquisition of Physics Knowledge	34
The Teaching of Mathematics as the Vehicle of Science.....	36
Mathematics as a Basic Tool for Physics.....	37
Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Performance.....	38
Socioeconomic Background and Students' Academic Performance.....	40
Concept of Physics and its Importance.....	44
Modern Trends in Teaching Physics and Teacher Characteristics.....	46
Appraisal of Literature Review/Gap to be Filled.....	47

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction.....	49
Research Design.....	49
Variables of the study.....	49
Population.....	49
Sampling Technique and Sample.....	49
Instrumentation.....	50
Validity of the Instrument.....	53
Reliability of Instrument.....	53
Method of Data Collection.....	53
Method of Data Analysis.....	54

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results and Discussion.....	55
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CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction.....	61
Summary of the Findings.....	61
Conclusion.....	61
Implications of the Findings of the Study.....	62
Limitations of the Study.....	62
Suggestions for Further Studies.....	63
Recommendations.....	63
References.....	64
Appendices.....	84

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1	Analysis of Enrolment, Number and Percentage Passes and Failure of Students in Physics in SSCE in Ekiti State of Nigeria between 20007 and 2012	5
Table 3.1	Mathematics Achievement Test Table of Specification	51
Table 3.2	Physics Achievement Test Table of Specification	52
Table 4.1	Correlation Matrix of Variables of Achievement in Physics	55
Table 4.2	Summary of Regression ANAOVA table indicating the prediction of the Criterion Variable (Students' Performance in Physics)	57
Table 4.3	Summary of Relative Contribution of School Factors and Student Factors to Students' Performance in Physics	59

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Science education system in Nigeria occupies an enviable position. Science is the bedrock on which modern day technological advancement is built on. Nigeria, like no other nations in the world depends on what Science, technology and Mathematics (STM) could offer for her national development. (Aluko 2001, Ajewole 2005). The above statement has been internationally recognized, which has made science and in particular physics to assume its prime position in the world today. Within the context of science education, physics has been recognized as an important subject and its importance to scientific and technological development cannot be overemphasized. Edmwoyi-out (2011) opines that it was as a result of the recognition given to science courses, especially physics in the development of the individual and the nation that is made a core - subject among the natural sciences and other science related courses in the Nigerian education system. Its inclusion as a core subject in science in the secondary school calls for the need to teach it effectively (as cited in Musyoki 2011). This is because effective science teaching can lead to the attainment of scientific and technological greatness.

The aims of education generally are both individual and cultural. Akinpelu (1991) asserted that the teaching of physics is designed to assist individual students to develop their skills and abilities so as to fulfill their potentials and to lead satisfying and productive lives (as cited in Fakeye, 2015). All these learning takes place in the school.

A school is an educational institution designed to purposefully provide learning spaces and learning environment for the teaching and learning of students under the direction of teachers. The school comprises of different classrooms, offices, libraries, laboratories, playing ground, among other facilities where students are taught in different disciplines. The facilities in the schools are meant for the purpose of smooth running of activities for which the school is established. Aremu (2001) opines that school could be publicly owned and administered by the government or private individuals. The school could be primary, secondary or tertiary institution. In this study, secondary school settings will be considered. Secondary education, as specified in the National Policy on Education, is to prepare students for useful living in the society and for higher education (FGN, 2004). The school related factors that will be discussed in this study includes; school environment, availability of instructional materials in schools and teachers'

qualification. School environment refers to diverse physical locations, contexts, and cultures in which students learn. Instructional materials are the tools used in educational lessons, which includes active learning and assessment. Basically, any resource a teacher uses to help him teach his students is an instructional material. Teachers' qualification on the other hand means all the skills a teacher required to teach effectively. Such skills include formal education, experience, subject matter knowledge, pedagogy studies, duration of training, certificate/licensing and professional development (Zuzovsky, 2009).

A student is a learner or someone who attends an educational institution. In this study, science students will be the focus, since they all offered physics in public examinations. Students' factors in this study are divided into students' background in mathematics, parental motivation, and parental socioeconomic status. Students' background knowledge in mathematics is the pre-existing knowledge, skills, beliefs and attitudes, which influence how they attend, interpret and organize in-coming information in physics. Parental motivation describes ways in which parents promote productivity in their children. This can be achieved by encouraging the children in spite of the recurrent poor academic performance of the children in the past. Socioeconomic status, on the other hand is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. It is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group. Parental educational level therefore refers to the highest *level* of schooling that the parents/guardians of the students have reached which sometimes affects their performance in school.

Physics is the study of systematized knowledge produced by careful observation, measurement and experiment which attempts to establish general laws or principles to describe phenomena under study (Ivowi, 1999 as cited by Obafemi and Ogunkunle, 2013). It is the study of matter, energy and the relationships between them, and find applications throughout the universe, since matter and energy constitutes our natural world. Physics is one of the basic sciences that touch our lives daily at every point. Physics is an interesting and indispensable subject because it studies the natural phenomenon around us and bridge the gap between the courses learnt in the classroom and the practical application in every human endeavour. The feats of science and technology are in every facet of human endeavour. It could be rightly said that every sector of the society now depends on science and technology for proper functioning and mathematics as the creation of human mind (Awofala, Arigbabu and Awofala, 2013).

Furthermore, physics is a course that is very interesting, vast, mathematical and experimental if the teacher can teach in a conducive atmosphere. Physics concepts have been considered difficult and unattractive by many students in secondary Schools (Angell, Guttersand, Henriksen, & Isnes, 2004). This could be attributed to the mathematical nature of physics where students have to learn and understand numerous theoretical concepts which are rooted in fundamental mathematics (Obafemi, 2005). The perception of students about physics as a difficult subject can also be attributed to the nonchalant attitude on the part of the physics teachers. Some teacher's attitude to the teaching of physics is very bad. This attitude should be corrected on the part of the teachers if the objective of teaching physics is to be achieved. Physics plays a major role in the proper understanding of technological subjects. It is a major contribution to technology through the nature of its discipline and its application in the field of engineering, medicine, architecture, manufacturing among others.

Similarly, another fundamental problem facing the teaching of physics today is the question of how current are the professional teachers. They have no knowledge of the current ideas and innovations that have taken place in the educational field in the recent past. What account for this is that teachers have not been given the opportunity for re-training (Ogunbiyi, 2004). He therefore recommended that teachers should be encouraged to go for workshop training in their areas of specialization.

Academic performance has been described as the scholastic standing of a student at a given moment (Daniels and Schouten 1970). This scholastic standing could be explained in terms of the grades obtained in a course or groups of courses. (Mallory 2014) argued that performance is a measure of output and that the main outputs in education are expressed in terms of learning, that is, changes in knowledge, skills and attitudes of individuals as a result of their experiences within the school's system. Academic performance is regarded a student's performance in an examination as being depended on his cumulative grade point average (Al-Shorayye 1995). Jansen (2004) defined academic performance as the process of developing the capacities and potentials of the individual student so as to prepare that individual to be successful in a specific society or culture. Student's success is generally judged by examination performance while the best criterion of performance is the sum of the student's academic performance in all the subjects taken. Poor academic performance according to Aremu (2000) is a performance that is adjudged by the examinee and some other significant as falling below an

expected standard. The interpretation of this expected or desired standard is better appreciated from the perpetual cognitive ability of the evaluator of the performance.

Academic performance of secondary school students in physics has not been encouraging. In Nigeria, in spite of the enormous role that Physics plays in national development and the efforts of government and other stake holders in improving science education, Physics results in public examinations like the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) have not been satisfactory. These have been attributed to many factors which include utilization of inappropriate teaching methods in schools, poor quality school science teachers and school location (Macmillan, 2012), poor teachers' performance in terms of accomplishing the teaching task, negative attitude to work and poor teaching habits which have been attributed to poor motivation (Ofoegbu, 2004). Resources available to teachers, general conditions of infrastructure as well as instructional materials in public secondary schools (PSS) in Nigeria are poor (Oredein, 2000). Teachers attribute which include teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, communication ability; emotional stability, good human relationship and interest in the job have significant relationship with students' academic performance (Bangbade 2004). The broad aims and expectations of any teaching and learning programme are productivity and positive-evaluated end product (achievement). But in recent times, students' achievement in the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by NECO and West African Examination Council (WAEC) has continued to deteriorate from year to year, particularly in Physics. In particular, reports on WAEC results of SSCE in Ekiti State over the years often revealed low performance of students in Physics. Parents and government are in total agreement that, despite their hug investment on education, students' performances still remain poor. Teachers, also complain of students' low performance at both internal and external examinations (Asikhia, 2010). Rena (2000) explained that for students to perform well in any examination one of the prerequisites is that their teachers must know them and have profound knowledge of their state of physical, intellectual and psychological readiness.

Table 1.1

Summary table showing the Analysis of Enrolment, Number and Percentage Passes and Failure of Students in Physics in SSCE in Ekiti State of Nigeria between 2007 and 2012.

YEAR	No of candidates registered	GRADE [A1- C6]	GRADE [D7- E8]	GRADE [F9]
2007	4435	2524 (56.9%)	1243 (28.0%)	668 (15.1%)
2008	3385	1274 (37.6%)	797 (23.5%)	1314 (38.9%)
2009	4289	2296 (53.5%)	1036 (28.7%)	957 (17.8%)
2010	5459	2569 (49.8%)	1825 (31.6%)	1065 (18.6%)
2011	6859	4020 (58.6%)	1124 (16.4%)	1715 (25.0%)
2012	5081	2514 (49.5%)	1379 (27.1%)	1188 (23.4%)

Source: ESMET, 2013

A closer look at the table above shows the persistent low academic performance of students in Physics over the years of study in Senior Secondary Schools (SSS) in Ekiti State. Since credit pass (A1-C6) grade is adjudged a better grade and usually requested for in the admission process as requirement for a related course of study in tertiary institution, not very many of the candidates were able to score the grade. The analysis of the number of the candidates that scored A1- C6 was as follows: In the year 2007, it was 2524 (56.9%); year 2008 was 1274 (37.6%); also year 2009 was 2296 (53.5%); year 2010 was 2569 (49.8%); also year 2011 was 4020 (58.6%); and finally, 2012 was 2514 (49.5%). It is observed that there was fluctuation in the performance of the students in Physics over the period involved in the above statistic.

Despite the importance of physics to mankind and the efforts of researchers to improve on its teaching and learning, the achievement of students in the subject remains low in Nigeria. Among the factors that have been identified by the researcher as factors contributing to the poor

performances of students in physics are school factors and students factors. The school factors include; school environment; availability of instructional materials for the teaching of physics and teacher; and teachers' qualification and experience. The student factors identified in this study are; students' background in mathematics, parental motivation and parent socioeconomic status.

According to Stoops and Johnson (1989) cited in Adeyemo (2010), the school environment affects students' education, their conduct. School environment plays major role in the life of every student. Udoh (1980) in his article "The Environmental Health Problems in Nigeria Schools" identified some unhealthy practices in our schools (as cited in Orlu 2013). These include sitting of schools, inadequate facilities, poor ventilation, large class size, etc. Most of our schools have no light, insufficient facilities, dilapidated buildings and no ventilation. Under these conditions the health of students and teachers may be adversely affected, which will in turn reflect on students' performance.

The school administration also plays a significant role in determining students' academic achievement (Ololube and Kpolovie, 2012). The administrators decide the use of funds, acquisition of instructional materials and teaching aids, employment of both the quantity and quality of teachers, in truth, all materials and human resources that enter into the school premises.

Ojeritude (1997) cited in Adeyemo (2010) postulated that for formal education to be properly provided, schools should be built with necessary facilities to ensure enriched and enabling environment for teaching and learning. To him, any school suitable for academic work requires physical facilities such as properly constructed and equipped classroom furniture, games facilities, laboratories, and hostels with basic amenities and any other equipment necessary for teaching and learning. Unfortunately many schools operate without laboratories for science subjects and many other facilities. Classroom blocks are dilapidated and lack furniture. As a result, many students sit under trees, which serve as the umbrella for rain and sunshine. Inadequacy of space and facilities in schools can easily inhibit the productivity of both the teacher and the learner while a conducive learning environment would enhance the sustenance of interest, stimulate learning and ensure satisfactory development and academic performance.

Instructional materials are the tools used in educational institutions for teaching and learning in order to promote teachers' efficiency and improve students' performance. The

importance of instructional materials is to make learning more appealing, real and interesting. It improves student's knowledge, skills, ability and comprehension of information; and to contribute to their overall development and upbringing. It is also a tool used to clarify important concepts to arouse and sustain students' interest, give all students in a class the opportunity to share experiences necessary for new learning, and help make learning more permanent. Ibeneme (2000) affirms that instructional materials are those materials used for practical and demonstration in the class situation by students and teachers. Ikerionwu (2000) saw instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teacher to present a lesson to the learners in a logical and manner. Agina-Obu (2005) submitted that instructional materials of all kinds appeal to the sense organs during teaching and learning. Isola (2010) also described instructional materials as objects or devices that assist the teachers to present their lessons logically and sequentially to the learners. Oluwagbohunmi and Abdu-Raheem (2014) acknowledged that instructional materials are such used by teachers to aid explanations and make learning of subject matter understandable to students during teaching learning process.

In their own study, Olumorin, Yusuf, Ajidagba and Jekayinfa (2010) observed that instructional materials help teachers to teach conveniently and the learners to learn easily without any problem. They asserted that instructional materials have direct contact with all sense organs. Kochhar (2012) supported that instructional materials are very significant learning and teaching tools. He suggested the needs for teachers to find necessary materials for instruction to supplement what textbooks provide in order to broaden concepts and arouse students' interests in the subject. According to Abolade (2009), the advantages of instructional materials are that they are cheaper to produce, useful in teaching large number of students at a time, encourage learners to pay proper attention and enhance their interest.

Therefore, Ogbondah (2008) advocated for teachers' resourcefulness and also encouraged them to search for necessary instructional materials through local means to supplement or replace the standard ones. Oso (2011) also agreed that the best way for teachers to make use of their manipulative skills is to improvise so as to achieve their lesson objectives at least to a reasonable extent. Jekayinfa (2012) also identified the importance of improvisation of instructional materials as making learning concrete and real, substitutes one thing for another, allows the students to participate in the production of materials, economical and more teacher-student resource oriented. Abdu-Raheem (2014) submitted that improvisation of locally made

teaching aids could assist to improve quality of graduates turn out from schools and standard of education generally. Abdu-Raheem and Oluwagbohunmi (2015) also corroborated the idea that resourceful and skilful teachers should improvise necessary instructional materials to promote academic standard in Nigerian schools. Thus, for instructional materials to be of maximum benefit to the students, teachers at all levels must be sensitized on its importance in the educational system. It is not only instructional materials that influence students' academic performance; teachers are also major determinant of the performance of students in secondary schools.

Teachers have been universally accepted as one of the most important component of education because of the significant and valuable role of being the builders, pillars and makers of the society (Mkpanang 2015). The teacher imparts knowledge (education), which makes the role of the teacher of paramount importance both in the present and the future of a student. Afolabi (2009) asserted that teachers are basic tool in curriculum implementation which make them crucial factor that influence students' experience and achievement, and continuing educational development. Teachers' qualification is one of the critical factors that drive students' academic performance (Hakielimu, 2011). Eryilmaz and Laslan (1999) cited in Aina and Olanipekun (2015) observed that one of the most important factors in the teaching process is the qualification of the teacher. Ibrahim (2000) is of the view that teachers' qualifications can go a long way to bring about students' higher academic achievement.

Usman (2012) cited in Musau and Abere (2015) established that a qualified teacher is one who holds a teaching certificate that is licensed by the state and well competent in her area of specialization. Musau and Abere (2015) quotes the Pakistan Ministry of Education officials who described a qualified teacher as one who possesses knowledge of: the subject matter, human growth and development, ethical values, instructional planning and strategies, assessment, learning environment, communication and advocacy, collaboration and partnership, continuous professional development, code of conduct and skilful use of information communication technologies.

The educators, government, parents and society in general have constantly been interested in the academic achievement of students (Lydia and Nasongo, 2009). According to Adeyemi (2010), teachers play an important role in determining the students' academic achievement. Researchers have never reached a consensus on the specific teacher factors that

influence students' academic achievement (Rivkin, Hanushek and Kain, 2005). It was discovered in some studies that teachers' experience and educational qualifications significantly influenced students' academic achievement (Orodho, 2003; Ankomah, Koomson, Bosu, and Oduro, 2005; Asikhia, 2010). When conducting research on factors contributing to under achievement of Zambian female students in O-Level Physics examinations, Maguswi (2011) found that lack of qualified teachers of Physics had a significant contribution. Moreover, a study done by Adaramola and Obomanu (2011) found that lack of qualified teachers led to consistent poor performance of students in science subjects.

Teachers' year of experience is one of the teachers' qualifications indicators that is believed to be a significant determinant of students' academic performance. Greater teaching experience will produce students with higher achievement (Boyd, Landford, Loeb, Rockoff and Wyckoff, 2008). Studies have shown that inexperienced teachers are typically less efficient than the experienced teacher (Darling-Hammond, 2000). Studies have found a positive relationship between teachers' effectiveness and their years of experience and efficient teacher positively influence students' academic achievement (Agharuwhe, 2013).

However, there is the need for caution in Nigeria about the experience. Many teachers may have been in the teaching profession for over twenty years without properly developing themselves. This category of teachers may not be able to cope with the new trends in education. The subject curriculum is changing almost every year as the whole world is changing with technology. Therefore, it is better to say there is a positive relationship between experience and student achievement when there is adequate teacher professional and academic development.

Background knowledge is often referred to as prior knowledge. According to Schallert 2002 cited in ReLeah (2012), background knowledge is a collection of "abstracted residue" that has been formed from all of life's experiences. Human being, whether as a toddler or an adult, bring diverse bits of background knowledge, consciously or subconsciously to every subsequent experience, and use them to connect or glue new information to old. Background knowledge is an indispensable element in learning as it helps learners to bring new ideas and experiences from what had been learned previously. How important is background knowledge? According to ReLeah 2012, "What students *already know* about the content is one of the strongest indicators of how well they will learn new information relative to the content". He further asserted that comprehension is impossible without prior knowledge.

It is discovered that mathematics forms a strong foundation for the study of physics. Mathematics serves as a symbolic expression in physics to show the structure of relationship between different factors (Torigoe, 2008). Symbolic expression allows learners to have a better understanding of physics contents and improve their procedural knowledge to inter-relate various symbols when solving physics problems. Physics and mathematics are inseparable. Physical sciences cannot do without mathematics (Adesoji, 2008). This is because many of the expressions used in these subjects are lent from mathematics. Students' understanding of basic mathematical concepts influences greatly how they will cope with higher level materials where the application of these basic mathematical concepts are required especially when solving problems in physics. Thanormsuay (2010) discovered from his study that Science and Engineering students need strong mathematical background to succeed in their fields. Akatugba and Wallace (2009) in the same vein discovered that mathematical issues among others were associated with students' use of proportional reasoning in physics.

Mathematics is a compulsory subject at basic and secondary levels of education in Nigeria. It is seen as a fundamental subject that is necessary for the understanding of other fields of study such as science, technology, social sciences, medicine, etc. This is important for the development of science and technological literate citizens, who can think critically about complex issues, analyze and adapt to new situations, solve problems of various kinds and communicate their thinking effectively for the economy growth of the nation. This can only be achieved by improving on the science and mathematical process skills starting from the basic level. STAN (1992) referred to Mathematics as the central intellectual discipline of the technology societies. The knowledge of science and technology remains superficial without Mathematics. It therefore means that the position of Mathematics in secondary school curriculum in Nigeria is important for scientific development such that Scientists studying in all field of science interweave equations into their everyday theories. In his own opinion, Ojo (1986) cited in Bello and Ariyo, (2014) described it as a queen of science and it is commonly referred to as "the language of science" (Redish, 2005).

Student's mathematical abilities can be classified into three categories; conceptual understanding, procedural knowledge, and problem solving (NAEP 2003). Students demonstrate conceptual understanding when they provide evidence that they can recognize, label and generate examples of concepts, use and interrelate models, diagrams, manipulative and varied

representation of concepts; identify and apply principles, know and apply facts and definitions; compare and contrast, and integrate related concepts and principles; recognize, interpret and apply the signs, symbols and terms used to represent concepts. Conceptual understanding reflects a student's ability to reason in settings involving the careful application of concepts definition, relations or representations of either. Problem solving in mathematics is demonstrated by students when they recognize and formulate problems, determine the consistency of the data; use strategies, data, models; generate, extend and modify procedures; use reasoning in new settings; and judge the reasonableness and correctness of solutions (Ina 2014). Problem solving situations also require students to connect all their mathematical knowledge of concepts, procedures, reasoning, and communication skills to solve problems.

It is on this note that researchers like Adegoke (2009) observed that many students appear to lack the reasoning ability involved in the study of physics. They also have problems with the logical mathematics operations that are demanded in physics learning. Similarly, Brekke (2010) exclaimed "there is an urgent arithmetic crisis in our nation". He lamented that a number of students who came from elementary to high school are deficient in basic mathematics facts such as the result of dividing a number by zero. Most students finding Physics interesting but have trouble with the mathematics used in physics. Most students will concede they understand the concepts of physics, but they do not know how to show mathematically, the 'hows' and 'whys' of physics. This view agrees with the findings of Obafemi (2005), where 90% of students complained about the cumbersome and rigorous nature of physics concepts in which someone cannot solve a problem without using a formula, almost all the topics have several formulae and someone must be really clever not to interchange one formula for another. Again, Owolabi (2008) discovered that students are deficient in mathematical concepts consequently, they perform poorly in physics. Similarly, Ighomereho (2005) found that students who perform poorly in physics have inadequate background in mathematics. Apart from students' background in mathematics, parental motivation is another factor that predicts students' academic performance in secondary school physics.

Parents' motivation is another student factor that influences the academic achievement of students. Students under motivated condition, exhibits purposeful behaviour aimed at achieving academic set goals. Eamon (2005) affirmed that supportive and attentive parenting practices positively affect academic achievement. Also, high parental aspirations have been associated

with increasing students' interest in education (Majoribanks, 2005). The effect of parental motivation and involvement in their children's school has on academic achievement is less clear (Domina 2005), parental motivation and involvement in school has been linked to both positive and negative influences on academic achievement (McNeal, 2001 and Domina, 2005). Explanations for this discrepancy are not conclusive. It is thought that the type of involvement and motivation may make a difference and that in some cases parents become involved after their child has already had academic difficulties. Other recent research has found more conclusively that while parental motivation may not help academic achievement, it does help prevent behavioural problems (Domina, 2005).

Douglas (1984) as cited in Omeh (2010) established a positive correlation between children's academic achievement and motivation. The author laid considerable emphasis upon parental interest as a factor governing children's chances of being awarded grammar school admissions. For the author, the simple most important factor that influences educational attainment of children appears to be the degree of parents' interest in their children's education. Douglas further stated that middle class parents express great interest in their children's education as indicated by more frequent visits to school to discuss children's progress, buying relevant textbooks and other necessary materials needed in the school for their children. The author also found from his study that parental interest and encouragement become increasingly important as a spur to high attainment as the children grow older. He also attached importance to the child's early years, since in many cases, performance during the first years of school is reflected throughout the secondary school. He suggested that during primary socialization, middle-class children receive greater attention and stimulus from their parents. This forms basis for high achievement in the educational system.

Parent involvement in a child's early education is consistently found to be positively associated with a child's academic performance (Hill & Craft, 2003). Specifically, children whose parents are more involved in their education have higher levels of academic performance than children whose parents are involved to a lesser degree. The influence of parent involvement on academic success has not only been noted among researchers, but also among policy makers who have integrated efforts aimed at increasing parent involvement into broader educational policy initiatives. Coupled with these findings of the importance of early academic success, a child's academic success has been found to be relatively stable after early elementary school

(Entwisle & Hayduk, 1988; Pedersen, Faucher, & Eaton, 1978 as cited in David, Susan, Terri & Susan 2010). Researchers have reported that parent-child interactions, specifically stimulating and responsive parenting practices, are important influences on a child's academic development (CECP, 2000). By examining specific parenting practices that are amenable to change, such as parent involvement, and the mechanisms by which these practices influence academic performance, programs may be developed to increase a child's academic performance.

Similarly, socioeconomic status of parents is another factor that influences academic performance of students. Such factors as parental education level, occupation, income, social class and type of parenthood are all embedded in socioeconomic status. These factors have a bearing also on the duration of the staying and achievement of the student at school. The type of family and level of parents education influence the choice of school they place their children. Hill & Craft, (2003) pointed out that socio economic status of parents has some influence on the academic performance of children. Children from families with low socio-economic status are at a greater risk of hunger, homeless, sickness, physical and mental disabilities, violence, teen parenthood, family stress and educational failure. Student from low socio economic background that encounter these environmental factors are four times more likely to have learning disabilities than students from high socio economic background while a combination of these environmental factors accelerate academic success. A student, who has not eaten for days and has clothes that do not fit, cannot maintain focus in a classroom. Anene (2005) argues that students from high social economics status compared to students from low social economic status families, that students coming from low socio economic background are not provided the same tools as the students from wealthy families; they are entering schools already behind those not living in similar conditions. Similarly it is believed that factors such as malnutrition, lack of motivation in homes, spousal violence, and single parents as well as impoverished home environment affects the development of intellectual ability negatively (Mario, 2006). This means that students from low socio-economic backgrounds tend to be below or just an average in their intellectual development particularly when this phenomenon is accessed in terms of scores or tests. Apart from the role home environment and parental plays in the educational success of secondary school students, school environment is also a major determinant of their academic performance.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is generally believed that Physics is abstract and difficult to understand. This belief is passed down from one generation to another and creates fear in students. Apart from this, many students have poor background in Mathematics, many were taught by teachers that were not so good in Mathematics despite the fact that they read Mathematics, while some teachers were forced to teach Mathematics which was not their discipline. In spite of the enormous role that physics provides for national development, the result has not been satisfactory. In a situation where the students will be blamed for the poor performance, emphasis is only placed on the student's cognitive or intellectual ability. Little or no attention is given to the fact that the student's background in mathematics, school environment and other environmental factors can affect their performance in physics.

Therefore, the study sought to establish determinants of low achievement in Physics despite concerted efforts by stakeholders to provide resources and other components aimed at enhancing its achievement.

1.3 Research Questions

- i. What is the pattern of relationship among school related factors (school environment, availability of instructional materials and teacher qualification), student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) and students' performance in physics in Ekiti State?
- ii. What is the composite contribution of school related factors ((school environment, availability of instructional materials and teacher qualification) and student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) in the prediction of students' performance in physics in Ekiti State?
- iii. What is the relative contribution of school related factors ((school environment, availability of instructional materials and teacher qualification) and student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) in the prediction of students' performance in physics in Ekiti State?
- iv. Which of the predictor variables best predict students' performance in physics?

1.4 Scope of the study

The study is limited to the senior secondary schools students in Ekiti State offering mathematics and physics. This study is interested in investigating the influence of school and students' related factors as predictor of the performance of students in physics.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study is important to all stakeholders in education as it provides a better understanding on the relationship between students' variables in several ways. The result of the study will provide an empirical basis for development and improvement of student's performance in physics.

Significant number of students with difficulties in Physics requires a better attention to overcome their challenges and be more fulfilled in their respective aspiration in life. This study will go a long way to bring relief to many concerned parents that have children with consistent low performance in Physics. Also, our economy requires more manpower to develop and sustain growth in terms of technology; this study will help students to develop confidence, re-discover themselves and rigorously pursue their intending dreams.

Furthermore, it will serve as an eye-opener to the government to see another avenue to improve the lot of so many students that could bring our nation to an enviable position in the committee of developed nations. Government will see the reason to be more proactive and committed to the needs of our students by employing more teachers and developing them professionally so that they will not write students off even if they have challenges with Physics. Curriculum developers will also see the need to introduce basic mathematical concepts for science students to aid as many that will delve into the area of physics in the future.

Lastly, teachers will be well-positioned to erase the erroneous belief in students mind and encourage them to develop positive attitude towards learning Physics.

1.6 Operational Definition of Terms

Academic Performance: This is the score a child or individual obtain in test or examination based on his or her learning experiences.

Environment: The concept environment refers to the surrounding of secondary schools in Ekiti State. It can also be defined as the conditions that affect the behaviour and development of students.

Influence: The concept of influence, as related directly to this study, refers to the power the environment has on the academic performance of students, more especially, in Ekiti State.

Instructional Materials: These are non-human materials used to ease, encourage, improved and promote teaching and learning of physics in Ekiti State Secondary Schools.

Background in Mathematics: Student background in mathematics is the pre-existing knowledge, skills, beliefs and attitudes which influence how they attend, interpret and organize in-coming information in physics.

Parental involvement: Parental involvement refers to participation of parents in every facet of children's education and development from birth to adulthood.

Performance: Performance as directly related to this study can also be defined as how well or badly students do in their academic work.

Public school: This is a school formally supported by government especially in terms of teachers' employment.

Physics: Physics is a natural science that involves the study of matter and its motion through space and time, along with related concepts such as energy and force.

Socioeconomic status: *Socioeconomic status* is the social standing or class of an individual or group. In this study, it is a combination of education, income and occupation.

1.7 Acronyms and Abbreviation

E S M E T	=	Ekiti State Ministry of Education and Technology
E S S R	=	Education Sector Status Report
E S W L G	=	Ekiti South West Local Government
F G N	=	Federal Government of Nigeria
M A T	=	Mathematics Achievement Test
N E C O	=	National Examination Council
N P E	=	National Policy on Education
P A T	=	Physics Achievement Test
P S S	=	Public Secondary Schools

SEQ	=	School Environment Questionnaire
SES	=	Socio-economic Status
SPIQ	=	Students' Parental Influence Questionnaire
SSCE	=	Senior Secondary School Certificate
SSS	=	Senior Secondary School
STAN	=	Science Teachers Association of Nigeria
STM	=	Science, Technology and Mathematics
SMASSE	=	Strengthening Mathematics and Science in Secondary Education
WAEC	=	West African Examination Council
WASSCE	=	West African Senior School Certificate Examination
MLA	=	Mastery Learning Approach

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses the related concepts and findings from various literature and studies from books, journals and on-line resources to measure how schools and students factors predicts students academic performance in secondary school physics.

This literature review therefore examines the following;

- 2.0 Introduction
- 2.1 Theoretical Background
 - 2.1.1 Skinnerian Environmental Theory
 - 2.1.2 Constructivism Learning Theory
- 2.2 Concept of School Related Factors and Teaching-learning Process
 - 2.2.1 School Environment as Determinants of Students Academic Performance
- 2.3 Instructional Materials and Students' Academic Performance
- 2.4 Teachers' Qualification and Students' Academic Performance in Physics
- 2.5 Influence of Background Knowledge on Students' Acquisition of Physics Knowledge
 - 2.5.1 The Teaching of Mathematics as the Vehicle of Science
 - 2.5.2 Mathematics as a Basic Tool for Physics
- 2.6 Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Performance
- 2.7 Socioeconomic Background and Students' Academic Performance
- 2.8 Concept of Physics and its Importance
 - 2.8.1 Modern Trends in Teaching Physics and Teacher Characteristics
- 2.9 Appraisal of Literature Review/Gap to be Filled

2.1 Theoretical Background

For this work to be intellectually sound, it must include a scientifically based theoretical framework with which a systematic analysis will be carried out. Therefore, the following theories are adopted for the study:

- i. Skinnerian environmental theory
- ii. Constructivism learning theory

2.1.1 Skinnerian Environmental Theory

This section is based on the fact that environment is vital for the achievement of educational goal. This becomes necessary since one of the variables under school related factors in this study is school environment.

Skinner postulated that experience and learning are basic and very essential to understanding of human behaviour. The environmental approaches conceive human behaviour as something that is acquired through the process of interaction with the environment, rather than inherited. According to this model, behavioural development is controlled by and is a function of the physical and psycho-social environment, Labara in Eze (2010). Students' development is believed to be shaped by the pattern of reinforcement it receives from the environment. Skinner (1948) contributed in shaping the views expressed by environmental approach.

To establish his claims, Skinner performed many experiments with pigeons and white rats in the laboratory. He constructed a box (Skinner box) with a small lever inside it. The lever releases food to the animals whenever the lever is pressed. In one of the experiments, a hungry rat is placed in the box and if the rat presses the lever, the food would drop for it. The lever in this box is mechanically connected to a device that automatically records every attempt the rat made.

In the box the rat moved around tirelessly and each time the lever is pressed, the food falls for the rat. The rat becomes persistent in pressing the lever so that the food could fall. The food that comes down for the rat reinforces its action; this lever pressing becomes a conditioned response for the rat. In contrast, if the food is not accompanied with the pressing of lever, the number of presses would fall gradually to the lowest point. In this type of theory, it is the result or consequence of a behaviour that makes that behaviour more likely to be repeated on learned. If the result of behaviour is gratifying, one is likely to respond the same way the next time one encounters that stimulus. In the above experiment, the pressing of lever becomes instrument (instrumental).

Skinner in this theory identified the two types of reinforcers, they are positive and negative reinforcers. The stimulus that occurs after a response is called a reinforcer. Giving a pleasant or complimentary remark to a student for scoring a good mark in an assignment or homework is a positive reinforcer. By this action, it is likely that such a student will want to continue doing his/her assignment promptly. However, the student who receives punishment for

misbehaving in the classroom is not likely to repeat the action for which he/she has received unpleasant/negative reward.

Classroom Implications of Skinnerian Environmental Theory

The teacher should know that the environment or the conditions in which the students learn are very significant to the learning outcomes, hence, the teacher should provide conducive learning environment and conditions for his/her students.

- i. Children develop new behaviour by observing other people's behaviour and by observing the reinforcing or punishing experience of others. Teacher should be a model worthy of emulating to the students.
- ii. Reinforcement is an essential factor if the students must perform well in a given task. To this end, the teacher should not neglect the use of motivation that can adequately propel the students into actions.
- iii. If a student engages in a disruptive behaviour, the teacher should not reinforce such behaviour rather; he/she should endeavour to tell such a student the dire consequence of that action.
- iv. When there is interference in the transfer of experiences by the learners, the teacher may use explanations and reinforcement to strengthen the desired facts and weaken the undesired one.

2.1.2 Constructivism Learning Theory

Constructivism is a learning theory which explains how people might acquire knowledge and learn. The theory suggests that human construct knowledge and meaning from their experience. Constructivism's central idea is that human learning is *constructed*, that learners build new knowledge upon the foundation of previous learning. The learner selects and transforms information, constructs hypotheses, and makes decisions, relying on a cognitive structure to do so. This theory applies to the present study since one of the variables under student related factors is students' background in mathematics.

One of the major contributors to the theory of constructivism is Jerome Brunner. His area of interest was on Child development research, which originated from a conference focused on science and mathematics learning.

Bruner introduced the concept of learning by discovery. Bruner is of the view that learning is effectively engaged in if the learner is giving the opportunity to discover facts by him/herself. Bruner argues that mere presentation of information will not enhance effective solution of a problem. The theory stresses cognitive effectiveness. Because of this, some referred to Bruner's theory of learning as Bruner's theory of cognitive development. Bruner believed that learning by discovery begins when science teacher purposefully (i.e. intentionally) create (present) a problem and present it to the students by introducing some inconsistencies (i.e. contradictions) among source of information which are giving in the process of instruction. According to Bruner such inconsistencies lead to intellectual discomfort that will stimulate (i.e. motivate) the students to initiate individual discoveries through cognitive restructuring.

The intellectual discomfort created by the inconsistencies makes the learner to attempt to bring order out of this confusion by engaging in mental processes i.e. discovery activities which involve observation, hypothesizing, measuring, stating problem, data collection, classifying, inferring, etc. Through mental processes, the student can generate facts from his/her desperate experiences. Experiences gained during the mental processes enable the students to sense the disparity.

Two important notions orbit around the simple idea of constructed knowledge. The first is that learners construct new understandings using what they already know. There is no *tabula rasa* on which new knowledge is etched. Rather, learners come to learning situations with knowledge gained from previous experience, and that prior knowledge influences what new or modified knowledge they will construct from new learning experiences.

The second notion is that learning is active rather than passive. Learners confront their understanding in light of what they encounter in the new learning situation. If what learners encounter is inconsistent with their current understanding, their understanding can change to accommodate new experience. Learners remain active throughout this process: they apply current understandings, note relevant elements in new learning experiences, judge the consistency of prior and emerging knowledge, and based on that judgment, they can modify knowledge.

According to Bruner there are two forms of discovery processes which are:

Assimilation:

This occurs when a student recognizes a new situation that is familiar to one of the elements in the existing structure of knowledge (i.e. cognitive structure) and he/she easily assimilates it.

Accommodation:

This occurs when a new situation (i.e. a new knowledge) is incompatible to the existing structure of knowledge (i.e. cognitive structure) the learner first restructures (i.e. reorganizes) his/her cognitive framework (i.e. cognitive structure) in order to be able to accommodate the new knowledge.

Classroom Applications of Constructivism

Learning theory of constructivism incorporates a learning process wherein the student gains their own conclusions through the creative aid of the teacher as a facilitator. The best way to plan teacher worksheets, lesson plans, and study skills for the students, is to create a curriculum which allows each student to solve problems while the teacher monitors and flexibly guides the students to the correct answer, while encouraging critical thinking.

Instead of having the students relying on someone else's information and accepting it as truth, the students should be exposed to data, primary sources, and the ability to interact with other students so that they can learn from the incorporation of their experiences. The classroom experience should be an invitation for a myriad of different backgrounds and the learning experience which allows the different backgrounds to come together and observe and analyse information and ideas.

Hands-on activities are the best for the classroom applications of constructivism, critical thinking and learning. Having observations take place with a daily journal helps the students to better understand how their own experiences contribute to the formation of their theories and observational notes, and then comparing them to another students' reiterates that different backgrounds and cultures create different outlooks, while neither is wrong, both should be respected.

Some strategies for classroom applications of constructivism for the teacher include having students working together and aiding to answer one another's questions. Another strategy includes designating one student as the "expert" on a subject and having them teach the class. The role of teachers is very important within the constructivism learning theory. Instead of giving a lecture the teachers in this theory function as facilitators whose role is to aid the student when it comes to their own understanding. This takes away focus from the teacher and lecture and puts it upon the student and their learning. The resources and lesson plans that must be initiated for this learning theory take a very different approach toward traditional learning as well. Instead of telling, the teacher must begin asking. Instead of answering questions that only align with their curriculum, the facilitator in this case must make it so that the student comes to the conclusions on their own instead of being told. Also, teachers are continually in conversation with the students, creating the learning experience that is open to new directions depending upon the needs of the student as the learning progresses. Teachers must challenge the student by making them effective critical thinkers and not being merely a "teacher" but also a mentor, a consultant, and a coach.

Finally, allowing students to work in groups or pairs and research controversial topics which they must then present to the class.

Relationship between Constructivism Learning Theory and the present Study

The science teacher should intentionally create or present problems to students either in form of apparent contradiction or inconsistency among sources of information which are giving in the process of instruction. Encouraging discovery learning in science class by science teachers will result into aiding problem solving. One of the major objectives of science teaching is creativity. Therefore, discovery learning encourages creativity. Students should be taught concepts in such a way that they have applicability beyond the situation in which they were learned. Retention of science concepts are aided by knowledge acquired through discovery learning. Teachers must encourage students to make intuitive guess more systematically.

Bruner supported a radical reorganization of the curriculum across all levels of education. Bruner advocated the fundamental structure of curriculum to begin with simple contents and later graduated to complex contents. That means that learning should proceed from simple to complex, from concrete to abstract, and from specific to general. Teaching should be inductive.

Bruner supported the spiral nature of curriculum as we have in our present science curriculum at all levels of education. Bruner's Constructivist Theory asserts that learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas based upon their current knowledge. Instruction can be made more efficient by providing a careful sequencing of materials to allow learners to build upon what they already know and go beyond the information they have been given to discover the key principles by themselves.

In relation to the present study, the application of Bruner's constructivist theory to learning will help the students to have a focused attention on the principles they learn and also increase and sustain students' attitude to learning environment. Secondly, Bruner's theory of learning by discovery and his theory of cognitive development suggested that instructions at all level should be geared towards the learning maturational development or cognitive operation. Bruner's theory is directly related to the present study: effect of students' background in mathematics on their academic performance in physics. From Bruner's theory, it has been asserted that, discovery learning encourages creativity. Students should be taught concepts in such a way that they have applicability beyond the situation in which they were learned. The application of mathematical concept learned in the preliminary class will help the learners in its application to physics concept. This is because constructivist theory's main theme is that learning is a process in which the learner is able to build on present and previous information. The student is able to take information, create ideas and make choices by utilizing a thought process. So, Bruner's theory is in support of the present study.

2.2 Concepts of School Related Factors and Teaching-learning Process

School related factors are those aspects within the students' surrounding at school that influence the process of teaching and learning. The school environment is an important aspect of educational planning. The quality of education not only depends on the teacher as reflected on performance of their duties, but also in the effective coordination of the school environment (Ajao, 2001)

It is believed that a well-planned school will gear up expected outcomes of education that will facilitate good social, political and economic emancipation, effective teaching and learning process and academic performance of pupils. Everything within the school environment has an influence on the teaching-learning process (Caroline, 2014).

In this study, school environment, instructional materials and teachers' qualification with their experience are some factors within the school environment that were found to have an influence on the process of teaching-learning hence the school factors remains an important area that should be studied and well managed to enhance students' academic performance (Kilel, 2012).

2.2.1 School Environment as Determinants of Students Academic Performance

Environment plays major role in the life of every individual whether a students, teachers, employer or employee. It brings about better performance in students. Therefore, for the students to carry his learning effectively and efficiently, it is necessary that learning takes place in a conducive environment. Angbing 2014 stated that the school and the classroom are the laboratories from where the teacher operates. Therefore, the skills and knowledge a physics teacher carries to the classroom would make further impact if the school and classroom(s) from where he/she teaches were conducive for teaching and learning.

School environment consist of both material and non-material resources in the school. It includes the teachers, peers, cohesiveness, the subjects, method of teaching. A healthy and attractive school environment makes for conducive learning and promotes students pride in their schools and their interest to stay in school (Mgbodile 2004). Caroline (2014) asserted that the image of a school is dependent on the quality of its infrastructure. The physical facilities of the school have a variety of effects on teachers, students and the teaching-learning process. They include; administration office, staffrooms and offices, classrooms, laboratories, workshop equipment stores, libraries, hostels, staff houses and school ground. Physical facilities are one of the stimulating factors that play a fundamental role in improving academic achievement in the school system. These include; school buildings, accommodation, classrooms, libraries, furniture, laboratories, recreational equipment, apparatus and other instructional materials. Furthermore, their availability, relevancy and sufficiency affect academic achievement positively. Poor school buildings and overcrowded classrooms affect academic achievement negatively. Taylor and Vlastos (2009) found the relationship between environment and design within the classroom from a theoretical perspective. They found that physical environment of the classroom acts as "Silent curriculum". It means that classroom environmental design can facilitate and improve the learning process like the overt curriculum.

Eric (2005) in an article, the role of the supportive school environment in promoting academic success postulates that the school environment has broad influence on students' learning and growth, including a significant aspect of their social, emotional and ethical development. When students find their school environment supportive and caring, they are less likely to become involved in substance abuse, violence and other problem behaviour. The findings of the research show that supportive schools foster these positive outcomes by promoting students sense of responsiveness and belongingness. These terms are used interchangeably here to refer to students' sense of being in a close, respectful relationship with peers and adult at school. Therefore, building in a school community is a means of fostering academic success. Students who experience their school as a caring community become more motivated and engage more actively in their learning with their colleagues in the class. In particular, students' active connection with teachers and their perceptions that teachers care about them are what stimulate their effort and engagement.

In another study, Owoeye (2011) showed that there is a significant difference between the academic achievement of students in rural and urban secondary schools as measured by senior school certificate examinations. To him, the geographical location of schools has a significant influence on the academic achievement of students. Also he pointed out that uneven distribution of resources, poor school mapping, facilities, problem of qualified teachers refusing appointment or not willing to perform well in isolated villages, lack of good road, poor communication, and nonchalant attitude of some communities to school among others are some of the factors contributed to a wide gap between rural and urban secondary schools. Schools located in rural areas lack qualified teachers. It is because; they do not want to go to rural areas that lack social amenities. They prefer to stay in urban schools. It is also observed that a lot of coaching of urban students is done to prepare them for public examinations, thus promoting the spirit of competition and rivalry that may be lacking in the rural pupils, probably, owing to limitations in exposure and experience. Also, the study has proven that students in urban areas had better academic achievement than their rural counterpart. In other word, students in urban locations have a very advantage of favourable learning environment that apparently enhance their academic performance.

Arul (2012) in a related study discovered that school environment and academic achievement of standard six students are related. The data from 400 sample participants is used

to determine the relationship between school environment and academic achievement. The result of this study indicated that there is no significant difference in the school environment of standard six students in term of gender, medium of instruction. But there is an important difference in the school environment of standard six students in term of locality of school. The urban students have better school environment than the rural students. The urban students are having a stressful environment in their day life very much because they are living in the mechanical and hurry burry life. So they feel school environment is not very convenient for their studies. Therefore, school environment enriched with modern facilities makes the student feel comfortable in their studies that result to high academic performance.

A research by Sunday (2012) revealed that there is a significant relationship between physical school environment and students' academic performance in senior secondary school physics. To him, the physical school environment has some influences on students' academic achievement in senior secondary school physics. The physical facilities, human resources, and the relationship among them determine the physical environment of the school. The result indicated that students with adequate laboratory facilities in physics perform better than those in school with less or without facilities, because laboratory forms part of and enrich the physical school environment. It was also discovered that poor facilities and inadequate space, as well as the arrangement of items including seats in the classroom, library and laboratory, would affect the organization of learning environment. Favourable school climate gives room for students to work hard and enhance their academic achievement.

Orlu (2013) conducted a research among six hundred teachers and students with the aim to find out environmental influence on the academic performance of secondary school students, in Port Harcourt local government area of river state. The result of this research indicated that the school environment has a significant influence on academic performance. The location of the school affects students' performance. For example, when a school is sited in a noisy area like an airport or in the heart of a city where activities disrupt the teaching-learning of the student. One will not expect such students in this area to be doing well academically. Noise in anything interferes with teaching/learning process.

Danial and Felix (2014) examined the impact of the school environment and peer influence on the students' academic performance. The study assessed school environment factors and peer influence in term of the level of psychological impact they have on learners. Twenty-

one public secondary schools established that school environment exert a potent influence on students' academic performance. The school as an institution of learning which also act as a second home for learners has been found to have a strong relationship with students' academic performance. Therefore, the head teacher and the teachers should provide a favourable learning environment where students are free to consult them when in need. They should also provide adequate education facilities that can arouse interest in the students and to motivate them to work hard. It is believed that a cordial relationship between the head teacher and students create an environment favourable to learning as discussions are encouraged, and learners are listened.

2.3 Instructional Materials and Students' Academic Performance

Science deals with the phenomena of nature. These phenomena cannot be studied effectively through abstract or theoretical discussions only. Currently, in all systems of education, Physics, Mathematics and Science teaching is set to involve practical work (Kwale SMASSE, 2005). Most science students find that actual objects, models, or living specimens make phenomena concrete enough to be understood (Trowbridge, 2004). According to Maundu, Muthwii and Sambili (2005), a classroom teacher requires various kinds of teaching resources such as textbooks, apparatus, chemicals, charts, models, motion pictures as well as facilities such as laboratories and others to enhance the effectiveness of his/her instruction. A resource is any source of information, expertise, supply or support. Instructional materials play an important role in enhancing the teaching/learning process by modifying the teaching and learning situation. The use of the instructional materials involves a broad range of the human senses at the same time in the learning process. This facilitates learning and helps in conveying the intended purpose. According to Gregg (1968), every bit of chemical knowledge is a direct result of one or more careful and unbiased experimental observations. Most of these observations are made by using at least one or more of the five senses. Students' performance in practical work is determined by proper use of laboratory tools and the correct execution of procedural techniques (filtration, titration, preparation of solutions) (Kwale SMASSE, 2005).

Instructional facilities according to Storm (1979), have been identified as very important variables in the teaching and learning of vocation programme through the world. Facilities according to the American Association for Vocational Instructional Materials (1979) are the classroom, laboratories, workshop and equipment. Faisal and Annutte (2001), Patrick (2001), in

their studies observed that decline in the performance of students is due to inadequate facilities. Maitarfsir (2003) states that lack of instructional materials to serve as teaching aids that facilitate quick understand of the subject matter in the classroom is a great impediment to conducive learning environment for STM education. He went further to put it that for effective STM learning relevant materials such as equipment in the laboratories, charts, diagrams, chemical, models, specimen, and for technology, technological device like computer, tape recorder and video cassette recorder must be made available in the classroom so as to assist students to have a design of what is taught in their mind. Various studies have shown that a proper use of teaching materials/aid will positively enhance the teaching and learning process in science (Dele, 1983, Okebukola1989 and Johnson 1991). In all, various reasons have been adduced as major factors among which is lack of necessary teaching materials/aids in our schools as responsible for the observed poor trend on students performances (Ajewole 1991 and Ivowi 1991). Futunbi (1996), put it that laboratory facilities and instructional performance materials to which students have been exposed have contributing factors to the student's academic achievement. Jimoh (1992) cited in Musa (2011) observed that poor laboratory facilities and lack of relevant textbooks are among factors that are responsible for low performance of students in physics, chemistry and Biology.

According to FME (2003), in its Education Sector Status Report (ESSR) noted with dismay the poor quality of inputs in public schools. According to the report, such poor quality inputs have negative impact on teaching and learning (school processes) and ultimately on achievement (output). Asuru (2000), put that on the negative slope of availability of school facilities on numeracy, it indicates that facilities in themselves may not make any positive impact on achievement unless they are effectively utilized. Anene (1997), examined the influence of laboratory experiment on the performance of the Nigeria secondary school students in WASC examination. He found that insufficient laboratory work is accountable for student's poor performance in chemistry. The availability of well-equipped chemistry laboratory is a sure pointer that adequate provision for student's practical work has been made. He went further to recommend that teacher should make effective use of the laboratory so as to enhance student's performance. Ezeirouma (1985) asserted that schools with well-equipped laboratories have significantly better school certificate results.

Bassey (2004) cited in Musa (2011), observed that most schools lacked textbooks and other types of instructional media for achievement of curriculum delivery. Odukwe (1999), regretted that many schools in Nigeria apart from the model school and Federal Government Colleges hardly have adequate material resources. Gidado (2005), states that in some rural schools, teachers and pupils read under trees. He went further argued that in some secondary schools; staff rooms are not enough to accommodate teachers. And in some teacher education institutions, it has been observed that lecture halls, classrooms, laboratories, hostels, staff quarters, offices and office equipment, generating plants etc are in most cases inadequate compared to the number of staff and students that make use to them. In some federal and state owned institutions, the ratio of student/staff to the available infrastructure is greatly inadequate. In the researcher's school there are students' populations of over 1500, with 9 classes, which means each class will have no less than 166 students.

Onyejiemezi (1981), Ibrahim (2005) and Atadoga (2007), ascertained that the use of teaching materials, be it visual, audio or audio visual materials, enhance effective learning of physics and contribute to the full potential of the learners. Effective learning cannot take place without availability of basic relevant learning materials. In addition to private studies, where teachers give the students tutorials, exercises and homework, the need for learning materials is imperative.

Ogunsheye (1990) called books veritable vehicles of communication and transmission of education, learning and culture in any society. Akujuo (1991) emphasis that books have been the basics tools for any educational development. Many studies and reports have confirmed the crisis of books and other learning materials. According to Adesina (1990) and Iyila (1995), most of the higher institutions of learning in Nigeria are facing the problem of acute shortage of essential books. While Gojeh (1993), noted that most college libraries have obsolete and insufficient collections, while some programmes in the colleges do not have books, journal and other reference materials to meet the needs of their patrons. According to Ayodele (2008), "a situation in which machine tools are lacking in technical colleges, where tractors and harvesters are not available in schools of agriculture, where computers are not known in commercial school. Shuaibu (2005), observe that for effective and meaningful learning to take place three factors are indispensable, namely: the teacher, the pupils and the instructional materials alongside the conducive environment.

2.4 Teachers' Qualification and Students' Academic Performance in Physics

Teachers cannot be dissociated from the schools they teach and academic results of schools. It would therefore be logical to use the standardized students' assessments results as the basis for judging the performance of teachers. Teachers should be celebrated and rewarded when their schools and teaching subjects are highly ranked. While appreciating the value of rewarding teachers who produce better results, teachers should also not escape a portion of blame when students perform poorly. It has been proved that teachers have an important influence on students' academic achievement. They play a crucial role in educational attainment because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action and principles based on practice during interaction with the students (Afe, 2001) cited in Igberadja (2016). In their study, Wright, Horn and Sanders (1997) concluded that the most important factor influencing student learning is the teacher. Teachers stand at the interface of the transmission of knowledge, values and skills in the learning process. If the teacher is ineffective, students under the teacher's tutelage will achieve inadequate progress academically. This is regardless of how similar or different the students are in terms of individual potential in academic achievement.

According to Rivkin, Hanusheck and Kain (2005), there has never been a consensus on the specific teacher factors that influence students' academic achievement. Researchers have examined the influence of teacher characteristics such as educational qualifications and teaching experience on students' academic achievement with varied findings.

According to *Longman Advanced American Dictionary*, to qualify is to have the right to do something. Thus a qualified mathematics teacher is one who has the right to teach mathematics. Although this right complies with the respective educational policies of each nation, there are two main and common components of the issue. These include the teacher's knowledge of the content, and the possession of appropriate teaching skills. More practically, this can be stated that a qualified secondary school mathematics teacher is one who majored or minored in mathematics.

In general, researchers have found that possessing a major or minor certificate in physics or science is related to increased student achievement in these subject areas (Alexander and Fuller, 2005). Few educators, economists, or politicians would argue with the contention that, all other things being equal, highly qualified teachers produce greater student achievement than comparatively less qualified teachers. Indeed, good teachers have distinguishable impacts on

student exam scores (Alexander and Fuller, 2005). On the other hand, having a qualified physics teacher in the classrooms is a problem almost everywhere.

Despite the fact that research findings strongly emphasize the importance of having qualified mathematics teachers in the classroom, there is an acute shortage of qualified physics teachers in most parts of both the developed and the developing countries. According to Bob (2007), in all parts of the world, attracting young or mature entrants into teaching is a major challenge. In Europe, the United States, in South and West Asia and in Sub-Saharan Africa, problems to recruit sufficient teachers still exist. In many countries and regions, recruitment to specialist subject areas at the secondary phase is particularly problematic (especially in physics and science). He also points out that the age profile of the teaching profession is also problematic with large percentages of teachers likely to retire in the coming decade. Many education systems are supplementing teachers with a growing cadre of para-professionals playing a variety of roles.

Yala and Wanjohi (2011) and Adeyemi (2010) found that teachers' experience and educational qualifications were the prime predictors of students' academic achievement. Teacher experience has a significant effect on pupil performance in secondary school. Experienced teachers have a richer background of experience to draw from and can contribute insight and ideas to the course of teaching and learning, are open to correction and are less dictatorial in classroom. Teachers' experience and student achievement was that students taught by more experienced teachers achieve at a higher level, because their teachers have mastered the content and acquired classroom management skills to deal with different types of classroom problems. Furthermore, more experienced teachers are considered to be more able to concentrate on the most appropriate way to teach particular topics to students who differ in their abilities, prior knowledge and backgrounds (Stringfield&Teddlie, 1991).

However, Raikin et al (2005) found that teachers' teaching experience and educational qualifications were not significantly related to students' achievement. Etsy (2005) study in Ghana found that the teacher factors that significantly contributed to low academic achievement were incidences of lateness to school, absenteeism, and inability to complete the syllabi. Scholars have posited that various factors related to the teachers' characteristics such as their qualification, age, experience, and gender affect the academic performance of students in Science Technical Education and Mathematics (STEM) courses.

Owolabi and Adebayo (2012) examined the effect of teacher's qualification on the performance of Senior Secondary School students in Physics. The results revealed that students taught by teachers with higher qualifications performed better than those taught by teachers with lower qualifications. The result also showed that teacher's gender has no effect on their ability to impact knowledge on the students, much as he/she is a skilled teacher in that field of study. Similarly, Unanma, Abugu, Dike, and Umeobika (2013) cited in Igberadja (2016) examined the relationship between Teacher's academic qualifications and academic achievement of Senior Secondary school Students in Chemistry. The findings of the research revealed that there was a positive relationship between the teacher's academic qualifications and student's academic achievement.

In addition, Nwosu (2000) cited in Igberadja (2016) investigated the relationship between the qualification of science teachers and students academic performance in science subjects. The study discovered that there is a significant relationship between the qualification of teacher and students' academic performance in science subjects. In same vein, the author also study on Teachers' Characteristics and Their Effects on Students' Achievements in Chemistry. The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of teacher qualification, experience and attitude on students' performance in chemistry. The findings of the study showed that teacher characteristics were more influential in predicting student performance than school factors.

Consequently, Ugbe (2000) carried a research on the influence of teachers' competence in students' academic performance in senior secondary school chemistry in Cross River State. The study revealed that there is a significant difference between the performance of students taught by a qualified teacher and students taught by unqualified teacher in chemistry. Also, there is a significant difference between the performance of students taught by experienced teacher and students taught by inexperienced teacher. Furthermore, Bolarinwa (2014) study titled Teachers Characteristics and Students' Performance Level in Senior Secondary School Financial Accounting. The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship that exists between teachers' characteristics (qualification, years of experience) and students' performance level in Senior Secondary School Financial Accounting. Findings revealed that a positive relationship exists between teachers' characteristics (Qualification and Experience) and performance level of the students in Financial Accounting. As well, Okoro, Ekanem, and Udoh (2012) study on Teacher Gender and the Academic Performance of Children in Primary Schools in Uyo

Metropolis, Akwalbom State, Nigeria. The results showed that teacher-pupil gender interactions do significantly affect pupil's academic performance.

2.5 Influence of Background Knowledge on Students' Acquisition of Physics Knowledge

Background knowledge is defined as a multidimensional and hierarchical entity that is dynamic in nature and consists of different types of knowledge and skills (Dochy 2002; Hailikari, Nevgi, Lindblom-Ylänne, 2007). It has long been considered the most important factor influencing learning and student achievement (Thompson, Zamboanga, 2003). The amount and quality of background knowledge positively influence both knowledge acquisition and the capacity to apply higher-order cognitive problem-solving skills. An essential factor in developing an integrated knowledge framework is to create a learning environment in which learning means actively constructing knowledge and skills on the basis of background knowledge. Inadequate or fragmented background knowledge is an important issue to consider because if there is a mismatch between the instructors' expectations of student knowledge and the students' actual knowledge base, learning may be hampered from the start of the studies. Trying to learn something without having adequate background knowledge or, worse, having misconceptions, may result in rote memorization. This type of surface learning may occur if students cannot relate the new knowledge to their existing knowledge frameworks (Weeks, Lyne & Torrance 2000).

In applied science education, such as physics, where knowledge is learned in order to be able to apply it, it is important for students to develop an integrated knowledge framework from the start of their studies. Therefore, deep-level understanding in basic courses is extremely important in promoting good quality learning because these courses usually form an important base for future learning (Nathanson, Paulhus & Williams 2004). Inadequate learning in basic courses may have long-term effects that get in the way of learning later in the students' studies (Kelly & Glaspole 2006). One way to enhance students' high quality learning may be the use of background knowledge assessment as a tool for evaluating the level of support a student will need (Sharif, Gifford, Morris & Barber 2007; Martens & Hermans 2000)

Background knowledge is the raw material that conditions learning. It acts as mental hooks for the lodging of new information and is the basic building block of content and skill knowledge. In the literature, the term background knowledge is often used interchangeably with prior knowledge. Here, the terms are used synonymously since they mean essentially the same thing. It is interesting to consider how researchers define the concept. Some simply define prior knowledge as what a person already knows about the content (Marzano, 2004; Stevens, 1980) while others have more complex definitions. For example, Biemans and Simons (1996) conceive of prior knowledge as “all knowledge learners have when entering a learning environment that is potentially relevant for acquiring new knowledge. Dochy and Alexander (1995) go further by claiming that prior knowledge is the whole of a person’s knowledge, including explicit and tacit knowledge, metacognitive and conceptual knowledge.

Another helpful perspective of background knowledge is evident in Australia’s Productive Pedagogies efforts. Gustafson and Branch (2002) refers to “high connection” and “low connection” learning. High connection learning gives students the opportunity to link their prior knowledge to the topics, skills, and competencies addressed in the classroom. By contrast, low connection learning introduces new information without any direct or explicit exploration of students’ background knowledge. Queensland educators are encouraged to teach productively by tapping student background knowledge.

Much of the research on background knowledge has focused on basic skills acquisition (Marzano, 2004). For example, we know that reading comprehension (in many subject areas, not just language arts) increases when background knowledge about a text’s content is engaged. Many studies suggest that mathematics instruction should build on students’ existing knowledge along with teaching computational algorithms (Ball, 1990; Carpenter & Fennema, 1992; Carpenter, Fennema, & Franke, 1994). This is because students often possess relevant information that can assist them in mastering new content. A case in point is that many children have informal methods for working with math in their everyday lives. Such knowledge can be engaged when the formal symbol systems are taught. Younger students might explain how they know the number of classmates stepping on and off a school bus. Older youth can be asked about financial approaches to buying a car. For those struggling with mathematics using student think out loud and explicit instruction have been shown to enhance background knowledge (Clark,

2007). It is also important that teachers teach and ask their students to use the language of mathematics and the actual vocabulary encountered in the classroom and text.

2.5.1 The Teaching of Mathematics as the Vehicle of Science

Mathematics is commonly referred to as “the language of science” (Redish, 2005). The control tool of mathematics remains the basic skills underlying all scientific and technological skills. Mathematics is a subject that is related to other science subjects such as physics and chemistry in areas like Number and numeration–fractions, logarithms indices, Algebraic processes – solution of equations, variation, graph, and also in volume and students often perform poorly in the sciences (Jegede, Okota & Eniayeju1992; Mkpanang, 2005). Mathematics and science in primary and secondary schools share common objectives and it is desirable, for a better academic achievement, for those who major in science to select mathematics as their minor as this will be of immense benefit. Physical sciences are deeply rooted in mathematics, and as such they should not be studied in isolation of mathematics.

Yeo (2013) opines that mathematics is an intrinsic component of science and serves as a universal language and indispensable source of intellectual tools. Mathematics is widely regarded as the language of science and technology. Mathematics is the bedrock that provides the spring board for the growth of technology; it is also the gate and key to sciences. The importance and contribution of mathematics to the modern culture of science and technology stated that that “Without Mathematics, there is no science and without science there is no modern technology and without modern technology there is no modern society. In other words, mathematics is the precursor and the Queen of science and technology and the indispensable single element in modern societal development”. Mathematics Education is therefore indispensable in nation building. Mathematics form a strong foundation for the study of physics either simple operations or more advanced all requires some form of mathematics.

Mathematics remains the bedrock of technological development. Mathematics is a core and compulsory subject for all secondary school students in Nigeria. It is a body of knowledge that deals with quantity, structure, size and space. It has been described as the key that unlocks the mystery of the subjects that shape and enhance logical thinking with its calculative inference and deductions (Exam Ethics Project, 2002). Ikeriondu (2006) observed that Mathematics offers the experience needed to develop ways of dealing with problems, not only at school but in all

aspects of life. It is a highly developed discipline and is indispensable in every aspect of human endeavour. Mathematics is a tool and language of science. As a vital tool for the understanding and application of science and technology, the discipline plays the vital role of a precursor to the much needed technological and of course national development, which has become an imperative in the developing nations of the world. It is the foundation upon which technology is built. It has important functions in this fast developing scientific world of civilization. Mathematics is an intellectually stimulating subject that affects every facet of human activity such as politics, economy, science and technology. Salman (2005) described it as a precursor of scientific discoveries and inventions. The learning of Mathematics has become imperative in every society if the citizens are to cope with the fast-changing development in science and technology. The importance of Mathematics to man may account for its inclusion in school curriculum as a compulsory subject for every child of school age to acquire the appropriate mathematical skills that will enable him cope with life challenges

2.5.2 Mathematics as a Basic Tool for Physics

The link between mathematics and physics is a strong one (Hutchings 1973). In fact, there are some topics in physics that appear exactly the way they are in mathematics such as linear motion, trigonometry and vectors. Students who score high in mathematics are likely to enrol and perform better in physics than those who do not perform well (Lyons 2005). The most distinctive feature of modern physics is its use of mathematics and experiments, in fact its joint use of them. The business of mathematics in physics has to do with construction of subsequent analysis of concepts that are applicable to any practical or theoretical situation (Hudson 1989).

Physics, like mathematics should be taught with all efforts being made to ensure that mathematical expressions introduced by physics teachers are not ambiguous and provide a direct relation with the physical world and direct environment of the learner (Lerner 1989). Mathematics is the language in which nature expresses its laws. Most experimental results in physics are numerical measurements. Theories in physics use mathematics to give numerical values to match these measurements. Physics relies upon mathematics to provide the logical framework in which physical laws may be precisely formulated and predictions quantified.

2.6 Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Performance

There is no exact and common definition of parental involvement in the literature. For example, LaRocque, Kleiman and Darling (2011), parental involvement is 'the parents' or caregivers' investment in the education of their children'. Alternatively, Christenson, Rounds and Gorney (1992) stated how parents play a role in their children's education, in both home-related and school-related. Parental involvement is parental intervention in their children's education in order to be able to obtain information about their children's academic growth and participation (Crozier, 1999). Parental involvement is an umbrella term that includes a variety of behaviours and activities of parents directly or indirectly related to the education of their children (Hill and Taylor 2004).

Parental involvement plays an important role in students' education, and the advantages of it for students are numerous (Jeynes, 2003, 2007). For example, parental involvement has a positive influence on the students' academic success (Fan & Chen, 2001; Jeynes, 2003; Jordan, Orozco, and Averett, 2001; Gonzalez-pienda, Nunez, Gonzalez-pumariiega, Alvarez, Roces, C. and Garcia, 2002; Henderson & Mapp, 2002). In particular, parental involvement has more effect on students' test scores than GPA (grade point average) (Jeynes, 2003). According to Shaver and Walls (1998), students with high levels of parental involvement are better in reading and mathematics than those with a low level of parental involvement.

Furthermore, Gonzalez-peinda et al. (2002) identified that parental involvement makes a positive contribution to students' academic achievement by affecting their academic self-concept which is of considerable importance in academic success. Even Hara and Burke (1998) claimed that the key to improvement of children's academic accomplishment is boosted parental involvement. In contrast, Bobbett, French, Achilles & Bobbett. (1995), found that the effect parental involvement has on students' academic achievement is not significant. Some researchers have even identified that when parents get involved with students' homework and communicate with school, it negatively affects the students' academic success by decreasing their test scores (Shumow & Miller, 2001). In addition, Cooper et al. (2000) found that direct parental involvement particularly negatively affects the students' academic achievement.

Moreover, when parents get involved, they make a contribution to their children's emotional development and behaviour, well-being, social skills (Sanders, 1998; Henderson & Mapp, 2002) and even school attendance (Haynes et al., 1989). According to Desimone (1999),

parents' participation in school activities may establish connections between teachers and parents that have a positive influence on teachers' impressions of and views about students. In all cases, the importance of relationships between parents and school is inarguable because "the family is the most important and most enduring resource in a child's life" and "family-school partnerships produce impressive results for children and teachers"

However, the effects of not all forms of involvement are statistically significant (Jeynes, 2011). For example, Jeynes identified that conversations about school between students and their parents and parental participation at school events have a statistically considerable influence on the students' academic achievement, whereas the effect of checking the students' homework by parents is not statistically significant. On the other hand, according to Jeynes (2007), the effect of parents' participation at school events on students' academic achievement is less than parents' expectancies and parental styles. Interestingly, parental expectancies and discussion have more influence on middle-income students' academic achievement than on low-income students' academic achievement (Desimone, 1999). Furthermore, Desimone (1999) identified that talking with their mother or both parents (mother and father together) positively affects the students' academic success, but discussion with only their father can lead to a reduction in the students' test scores. Also, the research conducted by Bobbett et al. (1995) showed that the effects of parental involvement can be different based on the students' ages. They found that the influence parental involvement has on secondary or high school students' academic success is not measurable.

According to Fan and Chen (2001), parental control is weakly related to pupils' academic success, while parental desire and hope for students' academic success is strongly related to students' academic success. They found that close parental control may even have a negative influence on students' academic achievement.

Finally, parental involvement plays an important role in general school culture. As Deal and Peterson (2009) stated: "A school, by its essential nature, must be an open system with highly permeable boundaries" and "parts of the school culture must reach out and connect with parents".

2.7 Socioeconomic Background and Students' Academic Performance

An explanation for differences in academic performance is parent's socio-economic status (parental education level, occupation, income, social class and type of parenthood). Coleman (1966) contended that schools bring little influence on students' academic achievement; and parents' socio-economic status is the key to that outcome. This has been confirmed by many studies. For instance, White and Kistner (1992) found that children tend to do well in school in homes where educated parents monitor and help their children's school work. Downey (1995), Honda (1996) and Gothic (1994) cited in Musa (2011) found out that there is positive relationship between parents' socio-economic status and children academic performance.

Ezeinuoma (1985), from their work indicate that there is a positive relationship between socio-economic status and student's success in the school and students' success in the school activities. They point out that students from higher socio-economic background leave school earlier than those of low status. Those families of high status prepare their children well ahead and more adequately equip them with materials needed for studies than the low income ones. Coleman (1940), Shaw (1943) and Collins (1957) in Musa (2011), carried out researches to determine the relationship between the socioeconomic background and students' achievement. They concluded that there is a close relationship between them.

On the other hand, Douglas (1964) agrees that although there is a relationship between parents' status and students' achievement in school, the relationship is not strong. He then stressed that there is evidence that extreme poverty of the environment leads to a determination in academic performance. He maintained that the values which families attach to school education determine the degree of motivation with which the students pursue such education and which have bearing on their performance.

Dubey (1979), hold similar view with Douglas, that parents from higher class may have facilities such as radio, television, video, reading corner with writing materials provided. Sometime such parents provide their children with a mini library. They claim that these resources help to prepare children for the learning process in schools. But a child from a lower class is handicapped in that, he may not have even one single textbook at home. This could be true because looking at the economic situation in our country today; the lower class families do not have these social amenities in their homes. Some parents do not have good food and shelter

for their families not to talk of equipping their children with educational materials. In fact, in our secondary schools either day or boarding some students do graduate without having access to a single textbook of their own. How then do we expect such students to perform well in their academic work?

Obanya (1985), asserted that it is known that parents from high status in Nigeria provide books and in various ways encourage their children to read, whereas children of the lower class are not giving adequate motivation by their poor parents. They have little or no access to books, educational materials and other supplements to reading readiness. The researcher is of the opinion that high socio-economic class in Nigeria do not only provide their children with learning facilities and equipment but, in addition sent them to the best school which are either private or public schools with well equipment for learning. In fact, even the few boarding schools we have in the country, majority of the students there are of the high socio-economic class.

Prewitt (1980), in his study carried out in Kenya, revealed that whether parents who utilize private schools and who deploy resources in a manner creating pre-school condition which are conducive to a successful school achievement provide initial advantages which are difficult to match among their poor uneducated and rural Keyans. This is applicable to Nigerian society today, that parents of a high socio-economic class are no longer sending their children to good schools in the country but, are now sending their children to schools in overseas living only the children of poor parents in public schools, especially the newly established day schools that have no equipment; facilities and qualified teachers, and today such students are been blame of poor performance.

Prewitt went further to states that families with a high social statusprepare their children more adequately than those of the lower class. As a result children coming from the former background are often more ready to learn and consequently stand a better chance of succeeding in their studies.

Rossi and Stringfield (1995), arrived at a similar conclusion; they found out that the higher the occupation of the bread-winner, the greater the level of achievement of the children. They gave reason that parents do not allow their children to receive less education than they themselves received. They further stressed that parents will do everything possible to equip their home and make sure that their children attend private school.

On the other hand, the research work conducted by Isah (1976) and Fika (1978) cited in Musa (2011), on “relationship between socio-economic status and students achievement” came out in a negative form. Isah. In his finding in Jalingo concluded that children of unskilled labourers and petty craftsmen performed better. Fika, also concluded that there was no correlation between parents status and students achievement. Lake (1979), confirmed that children from middle income homes do worse in school performance than children form richer homes. Socioeconomic background of the student is judged by the status and financial state of the students and ability of their parents to provide a better intellectual and stimulating learning environment.

Research findings have also shown that differential family backgrounds are sources of inequalities in school achievement (Breen and Jonsson, 2005). Musa (2011) asserted that student whose parents have attained high socio-economic status levels also tend to shown a high level of education performance. That is the major reason for a strong political opinion in favour of a more equitable distribution of educational opportunity in that even though opportunity for selective secondary schools was dependent on individual merit and achievement; these later have been found to be associated with socio-economic status background of students.

Kegan (1976), opined that children from achievement oriented homes where intellectual activity was praised would probably be more likely to master intellectual tasks than children from less achievement oriented homes in which such accomplishments are not regarded. He shows that children of middle class families and professionals manifest positive attitudes towards school education. It can thus be assumed that parents who have been to school and who place high value on school work will encourage their children. Though the parental attitude may increase a child’s desire to improve his cognitive skills; and the child’s dispositions should influence his motivation to strive for intellectual accomplishment. It may however, be interesting that there are other types of homes, where parents are illiterates, broken home due to divorce or separation etc. All these have their respective impacts on a student’s school achievements. Mhya & Gamba (1977), found that there is a marked difference in the educational achievement between the students who came from parents with an educational background and those who parents were not educated at all. They also found that parents without formal education have a negative attitude towards their children’s education that this influences their children’s academic performance negatively. But parents who have high education exhibit positive attitudes because

they have realized the importance of giving their children opportunities to attend school and at the same time encourage them to do well. Onyabe (1977), findings reveal that the higher the parent's western educational attainment, the higher also their children's academic achievement.

In a study of the effect of socio-economic status of the parents on the academic achievement of a child, Ezewu (1987), found a positive correlation between academic achievement and parent's economic status. Bello (1997), found that children from high economic background have a better chance of succeeding in school than low economic counterparts, having provides physical environment appropriate for the academic tasks at school. Odukwe(1999), confirmed that children from high economic background are able to be enrolled in lesson, able to buy necessary textbooks and stationary.

Musa (2011) asserted that another important difference between middle class and lower class families is in the kinds of activities parents tend to do with their children. Middle-class parents are likely to express high expectations for their children and to reward them for intellectual development. They are likely to provide good models for language use, to talk and read to their children frequently and to encourage reading and other learning activities. They have particularly apt to provide all sorts of learning materials for children at home, such as books, encyclopedias, records, puzzles, and increasingly computer. These parents are likely to expose their children to learning experiences outside the home, such as museums, concerts, and zoos. Middle class parents are likely to expect and demand high achievement from their children, working class and lower-class parents are more likely to demand good behaviour and obedience (Knapp and Woolverton, 1995). Heyne (1978), in his study found that students from families of different social class backgrounds achieved quite similarly during the school year. He went further to state that, over the summer, students from low income families lost much of the achievement they had gained, while those in wealthier families gained in achievement.

Awoyemi (1986), in his study found that family background had significant influence on student's classroom performance. He pointed out that a house within a given income is likely to spend more on food, considering the more mouths it has to feed. He concluded that students from high socio-economic background and who are few in the family perform better than those students from low socio-economic background and who are many in the family. Riedesel & Suydan (1969) cited in Musa (2011) reported that sociological and psychological researches have shown that socio-economic level of the family affects academic background and achievement.

Lawton (1968) showed that there is significant relationship between the school achievement and socioeconomic status of the family.

2.8 Concept of Physics and its Importance

According to Beauchamp (1981) there are three broad categories of knowledge which include humanities, natural science and social sciences. The natural sciences include mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology and even geology. These disciplines serve all other disciplines. From these basic divisions of knowledge come areas of applied (practical) knowledge which includes architecture, engineering, education and law among others.

According to Salleh (2004) Physics is a branch of knowledge about the material world. Nature provides all the material resources that human beings need to live and manage their living. The human beings-material resources interaction must be based on some understanding on the properties of matter, how they behave and the laws that they are subjected to. Physics is one of the sciences in the secondary school curriculum. Like other subjects it performs some vital roles which help in the achievement of some national goals. Goodstein (1999) cited in Muli (2012) believes that “a solid education in Physics is best conceivable preparation for the lifetime of rapid technological and social change that our young people must expect to face”.

The NERDC (2008) curriculum presents Physics as a body of knowledge about the physical environment. It employs a systematic scientific methodology of study to arouse learners’ way of reasoning and create a positive attitude. To this end the use of teacher/learner discussion, teacher demonstration and group/class experiments as methods of instruction is encouraged. The syllabus not only emphasizes the understanding of the fundamental scientific concept and principles, but also the experimental approach of investigation. The experimental approach should prepare the learner to present scientific concepts and ideals in the modern technology. Further the syllabus presents project work and this approach provides the learner with opportunities in undertaking investigations for purposes of finding solutions to problems. According to Salleh (2004) advancement in science and technology is coupled with the deterioration of the ecosystem and greater use of chemicals and technologies that affect our health systems, we therefore need the relevant science or physics knowledge and understanding that can help us understand the physical world around us.

According to Hooper (1971), it is not enough that a child should have knowledge of his needs; he must also be able to weigh one need against another and determine his priorities. The importance of physics for the economic development of all countries is clear. Physics is the most basic of sciences and its concepts and techniques underpin the progress of all other branches of science. It is also a cross-cutting discipline that has applications in many sectors of economic development, including health, agriculture, water, energy and information technology. And the application of science through technology is crucial for providing the infrastructure that all modern countries need. The role of science in sustainable development was recognized at the United Nations Millennium Summit in 2000. A careful analysis of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) that came out of the summit shows the importance of science and technology in meeting those goals and as a tool for economic growth. In October 2005, politicians, educators and physicists from all over the globe met in Durban, South Africa, to consider the role of physics in creating a sustainable future for developing countries. The perspective may offer some insights into the difference that physics can make.

Physics interprets natural phenomenon through principles, laws and mathematical concepts and its application has created comfort to the universe. The entire universe comprises of matter and energy, and the study of Physics simply involves relationship between matter and energy. To this end, Physics studies entire universe at microscopic and macroscopic levels, therefore, its importance demands overhauling because is a key that open into sciences and technology. Physics is therefore an important subject that helps people understand the increasingly technological changing society (Zhaoyao, 2002). Physics continues influences in medicinal methods including imaging techniques (X-rays, CT-scanning, ultra-sound techniques, MRI techniques) and diagnostic patient screening techniques (Freeman, 2012). The unravelling of DNA structure and the subsequent genome project required a significant input from Physics techniques (Stanley,2000). Electromagnetism is vital in generation of electricity, mobile phone communication, optical and satellite communication, portable electronics, radio and radar perception, and X-ray crystallography (Campbell, 2006). Laser applications are used in commerce and industry, continuing research into challenges posed by diseases such as cancer, Ebola, and HIV/AIDS, will require high precision equipment employing physics principles (Amadalo, Ocholla & Memba, 2012). Hence, the development of nations cannot be divorced from Physics *modus operandi*.

2.8.1 Modern Trends in Teaching Physics and Teacher Characteristics

Physics educators have advocated for the need to use student based activities to enhance retention. Pedagogy should therefore encourage the use of student centred approach to teaching of science subjects. Integration with other methods when teaching sciences should also be encouraged because not all areas in physics can be taught through activities. One such approach is mastery learning approach (MLA) (Wambugu & Koech 2007). One problem with conventional method of teaching physics lies in the presentation of materials (Mazur & Lorenzo 2006). Frequently, the materials learned in physics come right from the text books or lesson notes. That the traditional presentation is nearly always delivered as a monologue in front of a passive audience compounds the problem. Only exceptional teachers are able to hold the students for a long time without actively involving them and even then, the amount of retention is way below average (Flanders 1965). Retention of materials learned is clearly as a result of active participation by the learner and close association with the learning materials. It is also important for the teacher to start with what the students have in their cognitive structure and build on it (constructivism).

Serious teachers should teach with their content in the mind and their students at heart (Bhatt 2007). What all great teachers have in common is the love for their subject and an obvious satisfaction in arousing this love in their student and ability to convince them that what they are being taught is serious.

Today, science educators continue to value the importance of laboratory experiences and view the laboratory as an integral part of carefully planned science unit (Singer, Hilto & Schweingruber 2005). The teaching of physics through practical experiments has however been established for a long time to improve students' acquisition of science process and manipulative skills. Practical work forms a key component of teaching physics both at secondary and college level (Iraki 1994; Sneddon & Slaughter 2009). Laboratory work is a unique type of science instruction since it involves first hand experiences; it permits the students to participate in science as a way of thinking and investigating as well as developing better understanding of science concepts, principles and theories (Freedman 1981). Instructions using laboratory work provides concrete authentic experiences that aid students in comprehending phenomena that are under study in the curriculum and discussed in the classroom. It has been accepted since the 19th century that physics cannot be taught without direct practical work either in form of teacher led

demonstration or class experiment by the pupils. Science laboratory work seems to leave a lasting impression. Many of them enjoy laboratory work and prefer it to other modes of learning (Gardner & Gauld 1990). However, if laboratory work is to promote productive learning experiences, many important science education goals must be incorporated into the instructions such as the nature of science, science as inquiry and conceptual development of science (Blosser 1991). Huddson (1996) in Kuria (2014) suggests that the reason behind teaching of physics in a laboratory stems from the fact that teachers want to teach science subjects in an environment that mimics the way science is in ordinary day life.

Through in depth study of simple physical systems and their interactions, students gain direct experience with the process of science starting from their own observations. As observed by McDermott (1991), students develop physical concepts and interpret different forms of scientific explanatory models with predictive capability if this happens during active class participation. Learning involves not just teaching the concepts but also erasing misconceptions learnt earlier (Lillian & Shaffer 1996). One of the most recent instructional methods developed by Mazur group is peer instruction (PI) which involves learners sharing with others what they have learned focusing their attention on the underlying concepts (Mazur et al 2006). These modern trends in teaching are likely to determine the mode of instruction employed by teachers and consequently affect enrolment and performance in physics.

2.9 Appraisal of Literature Review/Gap to be Filled

This chapter has reviewed literature related to this study. The reviewed literature shows that there are various schools and students related factors which influence the teaching and learning of physics. It shows that good school environment contribute immensely to higher level of educational performance. It also discusses the effect of building, library services, school location and school facilities with regard to student performance. The importance of the use of teaching resources when teaching physics was presented. It also pointed out that teachers' qualification and experience has the tendency to influence students' performance. The influence of students' background in mathematics, coupled with their parental motivation, influence and socioeconomic status as it affects their performance in physics was also considered in this chapter.

Previous studies by other researchers were reviewed. However, no study known to the researcher has been conducted in Ekiti State on how the variables in this study influence physics teaching-learning process. To complement these studies, the researcher intends to find the relationship between school and students' related factors such as school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification and experience, student background in mathematics, and parental motivation, influence and socioeconomic status and the teaching learning process, and make recommendation on how to improve them to ensure quality standards are maintained and consequently fill the gap.

Under theoretical background, Skinnerian environmental theory and constructivism learning theory were reviewed. Skinnerian environmental theory argues that students' development is believed to be shaped by the pattern of reinforcement receives from the environment. Constructivism learning theory suggests that learners construct knowledge out of their experiences.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the procedure that was adopted in carrying out this study. It focuses on the research design, population of the study, sample and sampling technique, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

3.2 Research Design

The study adopted an ex post facto research design of survey research method because the researcher does not have control over the variables as their manipulation has already occurred.

3.3 Variables of the Study

Independent Variables

School Environment

Availability of Instructional Materials

Teachers' Qualification

Students' Background in Mathematics

Parental Motivation

Parental Socioeconomic Status

Dependent Variables

Students' Academic Performance in Physics

3.4 Population

The target population for this study comprised all public senior secondary school two students offering mathematics and physics; and their teachers in Ekiti State.

3.5 Sampling Technique and Sample

There are sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State. Simple random sampling technique was used to select four Local Government areas out of the sixteen Local Government areas. From the four local government areas, twelve schools were randomly selected. Also, simple random sampling technique was used to select all the physics students and their teachers in each of the selected schools. The total sample size for the study was four hundred and fifty students and twelve physics teachers

3.6 Instrumentation

Five instruments were used for the study

1. Students' Parental Influence Questionnaire (SPIQ)
2. School Environment Questionnaire (SEQ)
3. Physics Instructional Materials Checklist (PIMC)
4. Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT)
5. Physics Achievement Test (PAT)

3.6.1. Students' Parental Influence Questionnaire (SPIQ)

The instrument (Appendix I) was developed by researcher to elicit information on how parental motivation and influence affects students' performance in physics. The instrument was divided into three sections. Section A captured the biographic data of the respondents, while second section B elicits information on the socioeconomic status of the respondents' parents and section C was for questionnaire items and it captured information on parental influence and motivation of parents on their wards. Section A was designed to elicit information about the participant's school and class. Section B elicits information about the socioeconomic status of the respondents' parents. The parents' occupation and average monthly income items were an open-ended item; hence all sorts of occupations were allowed. SPIQ was drawn on a four-point Likert scale response format: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha, which gives 0.61.

3.6.2. School Environment Questionnaire (SEQ)

The instrument (Appendix II) was used to elicit information from physics teachers. The questionnaire is in three sections. Section A captured the general information of the teacher. Section B was on teacher qualification and Experience. Section C focused on school environment as it affects students' academic performance.

3.6.3 Physics Instructional Materials Checklist (PIMC)

The Checklist (Appendix III) was designed to elicit information on the availability of instructional materials for effective teaching of physics concepts in the classroom. It was used by the observer (researcher and the research assistants) in the various schools to check the availability of the identified instructional materials.

3.6.4 Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT)

MAT (Appendix IV) was constructed by the researcher using test blue print. Two hundred multiple choice items with four options (A, B, C, and D) were generated from Senior Secondary Schools II Mathematics syllabus. The validity of the MAT was ensured. The generated items were given to Mathematics experts as well as experienced secondary school Mathematics teachers for vetting. After carrying out the necessary amendment based on suggestions and corrections made, the items were trial tested on two hundred SS2 students from secondary schools similar to the targeted samples to establish both the difficulty indices and discriminating indices of each item. 30 out of the 82 items that survived with difficulty indices between 0.40 and 0.60 and discriminating indices of 0.3 and above were selected and was used for the study. The reliability coefficient was determined using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20) and the reliability coefficient gives 0.82.

Topics/Level of cognition	Knowledge 10.0%	Comprehension 26.7%	Application 30.0%	Analysis 23.3%	Synthesis 6.7%	Evaluation 3.3%	Total
Number and Numeration (33.3%)	1	4	2	3			10
Algebraic Processes (36.7%)			4	4	2	1	11
Geometry and Mensuration (10%)	1		2				3
Trigonometry 6.7%		2					2
Everyday Statistics (13.3%)	1	2	1				4
Total	3	8	9	7	2	1	30

Table 3.1: Table of Specification (MAT)

3.6.5 Physics Achievement Test (PAT)

PAT (Appendix V) was also constructed by the researcher using test blue print. Two hundred multiple choice items with four options (A, B, C, and D) were generated from Senior Secondary Schools II Physics syllabus. The validity of the PAT was ensured. The generated items were given to Physics experts as well as experienced secondary school Mathematics teachers for vetting. After carrying out the necessary amendment based on suggestions and corrections made, the items were trial tested on two hundred SS2 students from secondary schools similar to the targeted samples to establish both the difficulty indices and discriminating indices of each item. 30 out of the 93 items that survived with difficulty indices between 0.40 and 0.60 and discriminating indices of 0.3 and above were selected and was used for the study. The reliability coefficient was determined using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20) and the reliability coefficient was 0.94.

Topics/Level of cognition	Knowledge 10.0%	Comprehension 26.7%	Application 30.0%	Analysis 23.3%	Synthesis 6.7%	Evaluation 3.3%	Total
Interaction of Matter, Space and Time (17.5%)	4	2	2	1	-	-	11
Conservation Principles (35%)	3	2	2	1	1	-	9
Waves-motion without Material Transfer (35%)	3	1	-	1	-	-	5
Energy Quantization and Duality of Matter (2.3%)	1	2	-	-	-	-	3
Physics in Technology (10.2%)	-	2	-	-	-	-	2
Total	11	9	4	3	1	0	30

Table 3.2: Table of specification (PAT)

3.1 Validity of the Instrument

In order to ensure the face and content validity of the instruments, the drafted copy of the instruments were presented to experts in mathematics, physics and test construction. They were requested to validate the instrument on the basis of item clarity, item suitability and relevance to the study. These experts look at the purpose of the study and research questions. They equally look at the questionnaire and checklist items which resulted in the removal of some items to suit the study. The experts equally recommended for teachers questionnaire in order to compare the observed fact with the view of the teachers and students. Based on their comments and suggestions by the researcher's supervisor, the instruments were modified to suit the study.

3.2 Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the reliability of the MAT and PAT, the items were trial tested on two hundred SS2 students from secondary schools similar to the targeted samples to establish both the difficulty indices and discriminating indices of each item. Item analysis was done with difficulty indices between 0.40 and 0.60 and discriminating indices of 0.3 and above for both study. 30 out of the 82 items that survived in MAT were selected and used while 30 out of the 93 items that survived in PAT were used also for the study.

For the reliability of the questionnaire developed for the study, the researcher administered only the questionnaire to ten (10) Physics teacher and thirty (30) students from ten (10) public Senior Secondary Schools selected from Ibadan North East Local Government, Oyo State. These schools were chosen because they were situated outside the study area and they share the same characteristics with the schools selected for the main study. Cronbach Alpha internal consistency estimate was then used to determine the reliability of both teachers' questionnaire, students' questionnaire and the checklist which yielded coefficient index of 0.74, 0.68 and 0.65 respectively. These show a high reliability index. Therefore, the questionnaire tested is reliable.

3.9 Method of Data Collection

The researcher visited the schools and collected data objectively. Before administering the instrument, a letter of introduction from the Institute of Education, University of Ibadan was presented to the school authority. The purpose of the study was explained and their full cooperation was sought for the exercise. The instruments were administered to the respondents while the researcher waited and collected the filled instruments. The

administration of the instruments lasted for four weeks. However, the researcher exercised high level of perseverance and patience. Out of the 450 administered questionnaires and achievement tests, 416 were retrieved back from the students, leading to the loss of 34 of the instruments.

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the study was analyzed through Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression at 0.05 level of significance.

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the pattern of relationship among school related factors (school environment, availability of instructional materials and teachers qualification), student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parent socioeconomic status) and students’ performance in physics in Ekiti State?

Table 4.1: Correlation Matrix of Variables of Achievement in Physics

	SE	AIM	TQ	BM	PM	PSS	PATS
SE	1.000	.218**	.005	-.005	.011	-.091	-.023
AIM		1.000	-.071	.284**	-.176**	-.068	.226**
TQ			1.000	-.162**	-.084	-.080	.041
BM				1.000	-.162**	.144**	.718**
PM					1.000	.068	-.127**
PSS						1.000	.151**
PATS							1.000
Mean	47.37	32.12	4.83	13.86	38.47	11.45	13.37
SD	5.610	6.617	.377	6.002	9.218	5.498	5.862

KEY: SE = School Environment, AIM = Availability of Instructional Materials, TQ=Teachers’ Qualification, BM= Background in Mathematics, PM= Parental Motivation, PSS= Parental socioeconomic Status, PATS= Physics Achievement Test Scores.

Table 4.1 indicated summary of data analysis on the test of relationship between the six independent variables. The result of the table reveals that, there is an inter correlation among the variables. The result also reveals that there is positive relationship among (availability of instructional materials, teachers’ qualification, background in mathematics, parental socioeconomic status and students’ performance in Physics) while there is negative relationship among (school environment, parental motivation and students’ performance in Physics). The result also reveals that correlation coefficients shows that no two independent variables have same value of Pearson correlation index value that is more than 0.850, which shows that there is

no multicollinearity in each of the predictor variables that could be used for the prediction of students' academic performance in Physics

Discussion of Findings

The focus of this research question was to establish the pattern of relationship among school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers qualification, background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status on students performance in physics. The result of the study reveals that some school and students' factors had significant correlation with academic performance. The implication of this result is that physics students are aware of the factors that have the tendency of influencing their academic performance. This study supports the findings of Omeh (2010) who studied "influence of family background on the academic achievement of Senior Secondary School students". The findings of the study revealed that parental socioeconomic status have positive influence on the academic achievement of students. Also, Obafemi and Ogunkunle (2013) found that a sound background in mathematics will give students the ability to pursue their dream career in science and technology. They also postulated that the use of instructional materials that are student-centred, interactive and practical-oriented may enhance the performance of students in physics.

The result also reveals that teachers' qualification correlates with students' academic performance in physics but not significant. This implies that teachers who are teaching physics in Ekiti State are qualified. This study supports the findings of Gaji (2014) who found that there is a close relationship between students' academic achievement and teachers' qualification. His study shows that the qualification of teachers will improve their students' academic performance.

Likewise, Guga (1998) conducted several studies to find out the relationship between academic achievement and teachers' qualification. He asserted that education cannot be provided by just anybody, it requires a teacher who plans and delivers the lessons or instructions. This can only be achieved by qualified personnel with appropriate qualification. This result also agree with the study of Betts, Andrew and Lorien (2003) which suggest that teacher with emergency certification (unqualified or without teaching qualification) negatively influence middle and high school students. However, the findings of this study negate the submission of Musa (2011) who found that there is no significant relationship between the availability of instructional materials and students' academic performance.

Research Question 2: What is the composite contribution of school related factors (school environment, availability of instructional materials and teachers qualification), student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parent socioeconomic status) in the prediction of students' performance in physics in Ekiti State?

Table 4.2: Summary of Regression ANOVA table indicating the prediction of the criterion variable (Students' Performance in Physics)

R = .738^a
R Squared = .545
Adjusted R Square = .538
Standard Error of the Estimate = 3.989

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	7735.118	6	1289.186	81.026	.000 ^b
Residual	6459.744	406	15.911		
Total	14194.862	412			

Dependent Variable: Students Performance in Physics

Predictors: (Constant), Parental Socioeconomic Status, Availability of Instructional Materials, Teachers' Qualification, Parental Motivation, School Environment, Background in Mathematics
* = Significant at $P < 0.05$

Table 4.2 illustrate the multiple correlation (R), the multiple correlation squared (R^2) and the adjusted square multiple correlation (R_{adj}) which revealed how well the set of six predictor variables allowed reliable prediction of the criterion variable (students performance in physics). The value obtained revealed that the coefficient of Multiple Regression, $(R) = .738$, $(R^2) = .545$ and adjusted R square is $(R_{adj}) = .538$. The model has a positive correlation. Therefore the variance observed is .538 which account for 53.8% estimate of the total variation of student performance in Physics. Hence, it is attributable to the contribution of the predictor variables built into the regression model.

Furthermore, table 4.2 equally showed that F-test that examined the relationship to which the independent variables and dependent variable were linear. The F-ratio $(_{6,406}) = 81.026$, $p < 0.05$ was significant and allow for a reliable prediction of student performance in Physics.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis reveals that the independent variables (school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification, background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) significantly predicts students' academic performance in physics in Senior Secondary Schools at $p < 0.05$. R^2 which is the co-efficient of determination shows that the independent variables account for a high proportion of about 53.8% of physics students' performance. Also, the standard error of the estimated means is 3.989%. This implies that the independent variables are relevant towards the determination of the dependent measure students' academic performance in physics. The study is in line with the work of Bandele (2003) who noted that the importance of instructional materials cannot be overemphasized. The result also support the findings of Omeh (2010) that parental motivation and socioeconomic status influenced students' academic achievement. This study also supports the findings of Ogunleye, Awofala & Adekoya (2014) that there is significant positive relationship between students' background knowledge in mathematics and their physics scores. The study was also in agreement with the findings of Owolabi and Adebayo (2012) who examined the effect of teacher's qualification on the performance of Senior Secondary School students in Physics. The results revealed that students taught by teachers with higher qualifications performed better than those taught by teachers with lower qualifications.

Research Question 3: What is the relative contribution of school related factors (school environment, availability of instructional materials and teachers qualification), student related factors (background knowledge in mathematics, parental motivation and parent socioeconomic status) in the prediction of students' performance in physics in Ekiti State?

Table 4.3: Summary of Relative Contribution of school related factors and student related factors to student’s achievement in Physics

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std.Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-9.686	3.495		-2.771	.006
School Environment	-.025	.036	-.024	-.695	.488
Instructional Materials	.035	.032	.040	1.090	.276
Teachers’ Qualification	2.564	.532	.165	4.820	.000
Background in mathematics	.708	.035	.726	20.069	.000
Parental Motivation	.005	.022	.007	.213	.832
Parental Socioeconomic Status	.063	.037	.059	1.710	.088

Dependent Variable: Students Performance in Physics

Table 4.3 reports the standard beta (β) coefficients which give a measure of the contribution of each independent variable to the model as predictor of the dependent (criterion) variable. Table 4.3 reveals that, among the six independent variables (school environment, availability instructional materials, teachers’ qualification, background in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) only two factors significantly predicted the student performance in physics. These are: teachers’ qualification [$\beta = .165$, $t_{(406)} = 4.820$, $p < .05$], background in mathematics [$\beta = .726$, $t_{(406)} = 20.069$, $p < .05$]. Thus, teachers’ qualification and background in mathematics contributed significantly to the prediction of students’ performance in physics.

Discussion of Findings

The study indicated that the contributions of only two (teachers’ qualification and background in mathematics) out of the six independent variables significantly predict students performance in physics. This implies that teachers’ who studied physics are the ones teaching the physics students. Also, the physics students are proficient in mathematics and understand the language of calculations.. The study agrees with the findings of Ornek, Robinson and Hangan (2008) that the language of physics is mathematics. The study also support the view of Vogt (2001) and

Ehrenberg & Brewer (1994) which suggest that measures of teacher academic qualifications represent one of the best predictors of students' better performance.

Research Question 4: Which of the predictor variables best predicts students' performance in Physics?

Table 4.3 clearly indicates that background in mathematics [$\beta = .726$, $t_{(406)} = 20.069$, $p < .05$] best predict students' performance in physics. Hence, it is statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the regression analysis reveals that students background in mathematics best predict students' performance in physics. The educational implication of this is that mastering of the basic mathematics skills by the physics students is among the most important factors for success in physics in secondary school. Hence, there is need for coordination between the curricular of physics and mathematics at secondary school level. This will remove the difficulty of application of mathematics in physics. It will also help the students to transfer concepts, ideas and procedures learned in mathematics to a new and unanticipated situation in physics. This is in line with Liu and Liu (2011) that there is a strong interrelationship between physics and mathematics in historical view. Also, Izaak (2014) show that there is a positive relation between interest at Physics and knowledge of Mathematics basic concepts with students' ability to solve Physics problems.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the summary of the research findings, conclusions, recommendation and suggestion for further research. The main purpose of this study was to establish the key determinants of performance in physics in Ekiti State in an attempt to provide a way of remedying the persistent poor performance in the subject. Data for analysis was obtained through questionnaires, checklist and achievement test. Physics students and physics teachers were used as subjects of the study. Information obtained was analysed quantitatively with the aid of SPSS computer software.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

The study investigated schools and students related factors as predictors of students' performance in secondary school physics. Expost facto design of survey type was adopted. A total of 450 S.S. 2 students of physics in four local government areas of Ekiti State participated in the study. Collected data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regressions. Furthermore, findings from this study are as follows:

1. The study reveals that inter-correlation among each of the predictor variables (school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification, background in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status) in predicting the criterion variables (students' performance in physics) are linear and there is no multicollinearity between or among the variables of study.
2. The result of the model summary and ANOVA table of the six predictor variables that allowed for reliable predictions of the dependent variables of the student which is students' performance in physics are significant and allow prediction of the criterion variable.
3. The result of the findings reveals that students' background in mathematics significantly predicts students' performance in physics.

5.3 Conclusion

Based on the findings and discussions of the study, it could be concluded that; student background in mathematics has great influence on students' performance in physics. The

underlying assumption here is that where students have a solid background in mathematics, they will have a strong foundation for the study of physics. It is therefore expected that only schools with qualified mathematics teacher will have the opportunity to produce learners that have a better understanding of physics contents and improve their procedural knowledge to inter-relate various symbols during solving of physics problems.

5.4 Implications of the Findings of the Study

The findings of this study reveal some implications for schools, parents, teachers, principals and government. For the schools, the study revealed that school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification, background in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status, when join together could predict or influence students' performance in physics. This implies that only schools who provides conducive environment for learning, provides necessary learning materials, have qualified mathematics teachers will perform excellently in physics.

For the parents, if adequate attention is paid to the provision of necessary textbooks or other writing materials as well as helping the students' in the area of assignments, it will contribute positively to students' performance in physics.

To the government, if sufficient fund is released into public secondary schools to ensure that school environment is conducive for learning, qualified teachers are employed and paid as at when due as well as deployment of necessary teaching aids to the schools, they are bound to improve in their academic performance in physics.

To the teachers, only teachers who are qualified should teach their studied discipline in the schools to assist students in their academics. Also, teachers should have positive attitude to teaching and assist students when the need arises.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

The study was limited to only four local government areas out of the sixteen local governments in Ekiti State with twelve public secondary schools. The dependent variable considered is students' performance in physics. The study would have attained a broader perspective, be an eye opener, if more variables and local governments had been included.

5.6 Suggestions for further Studies

1. Further researches could be carried out in other part of the country in order to generalize the findings of the study.
2. The study focused on schools and students factors as predictors of students' performance in physics, with much attention on school environment, availability of instructional materials, teachers' qualification, background in mathematics, parental motivation and parental socioeconomic status. Other variables should therefore be considered in further studies to ascertain how students' performance in physics will be influenced.
3. The researcher is suggesting the same study should be carried out on physics in other states of Nigeria and in other discipline.

5.1 Recommendations

The following recommendations are proffered based on the findings of the study;

1. Government should ensure that necessary instructional materials and teaching aids such as textbooks, charts and visuals are provided to aid physics learning.
2. The government should make all effort to recruit qualified and experienced teachers to teach physics in all the public schools in the state.
3. Sound mathematics background should be ensured for physics students in order to enhance their performance in physics concept.
4. Physics teachers should endeavor to teach prerequisite mathematics concepts in physics before engaging in real physics teaching as this will allow for meaningful understanding and integration of mathematics concepts embedded in physics contents.
5. There should be an increased instructional supervision in physics and mathematics education in the state. This should be undertaken by knowledgeable supervisors in the subjects.
6. Parents should provide relevant textbook and writing materials for their children and give proper monitoring on how they study at home.

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APPENDICES
APPENDIX I

INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
STUDENT'S PARENTAL INFLUENCE QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

The purpose of this questionnaire is to elicit information on how parental motivation and influence affects performance of students in physics in your school.

Read each statement carefully and indicate your own opinion in the appropriate column provided by ticking (✓). The information will be treated with absolute confidentiality and is only meant for academic purpose.

SECTION A: PERSONAL DATA OF STUDENTS

1. Name of your School _____
2. Type of School: Public Private
3. Class _____

SECTION B: PARENTAL SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS

1. Indicate your family type: Nuclear Polygamous
2. How many children are there in your family; 1-4 5-8 9 and above
3. Where are your parents living? Urban Area Rural Area
4. Indicate your father's highest academic qualification
I. Primary school II. Secondary School III. NCE IV. OND
IV. First Degree V. Masters VI. Ph.D VII. Others _____
5. What is the occupation of you parent /guardian?

6. What is the average monthly income of your parents/guardian?
I Below N10,000.00 II. N10,000-20,000.00 III. N30,000.00-N40,000.00
N50,000-60,000 N70,000.00-N80,000.00 N90,000& above

SECTION C: PARENTAL INFLUENCE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

This section is made up of questions with response coded as follows:

Strongly Agree – (SA), Agree- (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

Please respond by marking a tick (√) against the response you think most appropriate

S/N	Parental involvement and academic performance	SA	A	D	SD
1	My parents always want their children to be educated				
2	My parents arrange for supportive teachers for the subjects which I find difficult in the school				
3	My parents guide me in school assignments				
4	My parents provide educational materials for my personal study				
5	My parents communicate with teacher about my academic progress				
6	Paying my school fees has been difficult since I'm under a single parent				
7	My performance is better academically when my school levies are paid promptly				
8	My parents' concern about my grades encourages me to do well academically				
9	Disagreement between my parents at home affects my performance in school				
10	I feel very comfortable when my parents visits me in school				
11	If I misbehave in school, my parents will be informed				
12	My parents explains difficult ideas to me when I don't understand				
13	My parents compliment me when I perform very well in school				
14	My parents always know how well I'm doing in school				
15	My parents have made suggestions to my teachers on how to improve my academic performance				
16	My parents assist me in my school assignment				
17	My parents attends P. T. A. meeting on my behalf				
18	My parent knows the schools' rules and regulations				
19	My parents make themselves available for my school open day				
20	My parents have conversation with me on what is being taught in school				
21	My parents encourages me to be the best in my class				
22	My parent consider my going to school unnecessary				
23	My efforts at schooling are being underrated by my parent and this decreases my interest to study				
24	My parents encourages me to keep the school rules and regulations				

APPENDIX II
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT QUESTIONNAIRE
(To be completed by Physics Teacher)

Dear Respondent,

The purpose of this questionnaire is to elicit information about your school environment as it affects students' academic performance. Your school has been chosen for this study among others. You are kindly requested to answer all the questions in each section honestly. The responses provided here will be strictly confidential and will be used only for academic purpose.

SECTION A: General information

1. What is your gender?

Male Female

2. How many lessons do you have per week?

Below 15 16-20 21-25 26-30 above 30

SECTION B: Teachers Qualification and Experience.

1. What is your highest level of academic qualification?

ND NCE HND PGD Bachelors
Masters Ph.D Others (please specify) _____

2. How long have you been teaching physics (in years?)

1-5 6-10 11-15 15-20 over 20

SECTION C: School Environment and Students' Academic Performance

This section is made up of questions with response coded as follows:

Strongly Agree – (SA), Agree- (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD).

Please respond by marking a tick (✓) against the response you think most appropriate.

S/N		SA	A	D	SD
1	The school has adequate materials for teaching physics				
2	The school is located in an environment that stimulates learning physics				
3	School building are conducive for physics teaching-learning process				
4	The school is located in a noisy environment				
5	The school compound is clean and tidy				
6	Textbooks are available for each students				
7	The school has a well-equipped library				
8	Most of the textbooks in the school library are obsolete				
9	The library is open for students to access				
10	The classroom condition (light, neatness and quality of seats) is up to the standard in the school				
11	The school is environmentally friendly				
12	The school is located in a quiet environment				
13	The school facilities are in good condition				
14	Audio visuals are provided for instructional processes in the school				
15	The number of students in the classrooms are suitable for the classroom size				
16	Charts are displayed in the class environment.				
17	The class has reading texts appropriate for students in my class				
18	The school provides computer instructional package for students				
19	The school has materials (e.g. books, wall charts) to teach physics				

APPENDIX III
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
PHYSICS INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS CHECKLIST (PIMC)

(To be completed by the Observer)

INSTRUCTION: The following are the list of instructional materials used in the teaching and learning of physics in secondary school. Please tick *available* if the school is able to provide the instruments at the point of observation, and tick *not available*, if the school is unable to provide any of the instruments at the point of observation.

Key: Available (AV)... If the instructional material is found in the school
 Not available (NA)... If the instructional material is not found in the school

S/N	RESOURCE ITEMS	AV	NA
1	Accumulator		
2	Ammeter		
3	Audio tape/recorder		
4	Beaker		
5	Bulb		
6	Bunsen burner		
7	Camera		
8	Charts		
9	Chemical balance		
10	Chemical cell/Battery		
11	Clamp		
12	Constantan wire		
13	Drawing board		
14	Funnel		
15	Glass cylinder		
16	Graph book/paper		
17	Hammer		
18	Hoffman voltmeter		
19	Jockey		
20	Key		
21	Lens		
22	Measuring tape		
23	Meter rule		
24	Optical pin		
25	Pendulum bob		
26	Pliers		
27	Potentiometer		
28	Pulley		
29	Radio		
30	Resistor		

31	Retort stand		
32	Ruler		
33	Spring balance		
34	Standard weight thread		
35	Stop watch/clock		
36	Test-tube		
37	Thermometer		
38	Triangular prism		
39	Turning forks		
40	Wheatstone bridge		

APPENDIX IV
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT TEST

INSTRUCTIONS: Attempt all questions

DURATION: 45 minutes

CLASS: S. S. 2

1. Correct 0.04945 to two significant figures. (a) 0.050 (b) 0.049 (c) 0.032 (d) 0.011
2. Simplify $\frac{5}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}}$
(a) $\frac{1}{6}(5\sqrt{3} - 3\sqrt{2})$ (b) $\frac{1}{6}(15\sqrt{3} - 6\sqrt{2})$ (c) $\frac{1}{6}(3\sqrt{2} - \sqrt{3})$ (d) $\frac{1}{6}(10\sqrt{3} - 9\sqrt{2})$
3. Solve $7\frac{1}{2} - (2\frac{1}{2} - 3) \div \frac{33}{2}$, correct to the nearest whole number. (a) 33 (b) 8 (c) 7 (d) 0
4. Simplify the expression $\log_{10}18 - \log_{10}2.88 + \log_{10}16$. (a) 31.12 (b) 3.112 (c) 2 (d) 1
5. Find the equation whose roots are 2 and $-3\frac{1}{2}$.
(a) $2x^2 + 3x + 14 = 0$ (b) $2x^2 + 5x + 7 = 0$ (c) $2x^2 + 5x - 7 = 0$ (d) $2x^2 + 5x - 14 = 0$
6. From a point M, N is 5km due west and 12 km due south. Find the distance between M and N
(a) 5km (b) 12 km (c) 13 km (d) 17 km
7. A fair die is tossed once. What is the probability of obtaining neither 5 nor 2?
(a) $\frac{5}{6}$ (b) $\frac{2}{3}$ (c) $\frac{1}{2}$ (d) $\frac{1}{6}$
8. Convert 101101_{two} to a number in base ten. (a) 61 (b) 46 (c) 45 (d) 44
9. Solve the equation $2^7 = 8^{5-x}$ (a) $\frac{5}{8}$ (b) $\frac{8}{3}$ (c) $\frac{3}{2}$ (d) $\frac{15}{4}$
10. Make p the subject of the relation $q = m + pk$
(a) $(q - m)/k$ (b) $(m - q)/k$ (c) $k(q + m)$ (d) $q/m - k$
11. The probabilities that John and James pass an examination are $\frac{3}{4}$ and $\frac{3}{5}$ respectively. Find the probability of both boys failing the examination. (a) $\frac{1}{10}$ (b) $\frac{3}{10}$ (c) $\frac{9}{20}$ (d) $\frac{11}{20}$
12. From a point X, 300m north of Y, a man walks eastwards to a place M which is 600 from Y. find the bearing of Y from M correct to the nearest degree. (a) 26° (b) 45° (c) 210° (d) 240°
13. Solve for y in the equations $2x - 3y = 22$
 $3x + 2y = 7$ (a) -5 (b) -4 (c) 4 (d) 5

14. Solve the equation $\frac{2y-1}{3} - \frac{3y-1}{4} = 1$ (a) 18 (b) 15 (c) 13 (d) -13
15. If $\log_9 x = 1.5$, find x (a) 27 (b) 36 (c) 36.5 (d) 39.5
16. A sequence is given by $2\frac{1}{2}, 5, 7\frac{1}{2}, \dots$ if the n th term is 25, find n . (a) 9 (b) 10 (c) 12 (d) 15
17. Find the mean of the numbers 1,3,4,8,8,4 and 7 (a) 4 (b) 5 (c) 6 (d) 7
18. A regular polygon has 9 sides. What is the size of one of its exterior angles?
(a) 20° (b) 40° (c) 90° (d) 140°
19. If $y \propto \frac{1}{x^2}$ and $y = 1\frac{1}{4}$ when $x = 4$, use the value of $x = \frac{1}{2}$ to find y
(a) $2\frac{1}{2}$ (b) 5 (c) 10 (d) 80
20. If $x\%$ of 240 equals 12, find x . (a) $x = 1$ (b) $x = 3$ (c) $x = 5$ (d) $x = 7$
21. Find the product of 0.0409 and 0.002 leaving your answer in the standard form.
(a) 8.6×10^{-6} (b) 8.6×10^{-5} (c) 8.6×10^{-4} (d) 8.6×10^5
22. Solve the inequality $1 - 2x < \frac{1}{3}$ (a) $x < \frac{2}{3}$ (b) $x < -\frac{2}{3}$ (c) $x > \frac{2}{3}$ (d) $x > -\frac{2}{3}$
23. What is the value of 3 in the number 42.7531? (a) $\frac{3}{10000}$ (b) $\frac{3}{1000}$ (c) $\frac{3}{100}$ (d) $\frac{3}{10}$
24. On a map, 1cm represents 5km. Find the area on the map that represents 100km^2 . (a) 4cm^2
(b) 8cm^2 (c) 16cm^2 (d) 36cm^2
25. If $\log(3x - 1) = 5$, find x . (a) 2.00 (b) 3.67 (c) 8.67 (d) 11.00
26. If $x + y = 12$ and $3x - y = 20$, find the value of $2x - y$. (a) 6 (b) 8 (c) 10 (d) 12.
27. A ladder 16m long leans against an electric pole. If the ladder makes an angle of 65° with the ground, how far up the electric pole does its top reach?
(a) 6.8m (b) 14.5m (c) 17.7m (d) 34.3m
28. Simplify $(\frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{3}) \times 4\frac{1}{3} \div 3\frac{1}{4}$ (a) $\frac{5}{9}$ (b) $\frac{5}{16}$ (c) $\frac{8}{13}$ (d) $\frac{16}{5}$

The table below gives the distribution of marks obtained by a number of pupils in a class test. Use the information to answer questions 2-4

Marks	0	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency	4	7	12	18	11	8

29. The mode of the distribution is (a) 3 (b) 5 (c) 8 (d) 18
30. Find the median of the distribution (a) 1 (b) 2 (c) 3 (d) 4

APPENDIX V
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR EDUCATIONAL EVALUATION
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION, UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
PHYSICS ACHIEVEMENT TEST

INSTRUCTIONS: Attempt all questions

DURATION: 45 minutes

CLASS: S. S. 2

1. The principle of moment states that (a) If a body is in equilibrium under the action of a number of parallel forces, sum of clockwise moment about a point equals sum of anticlockwise moment about the same point. (b) Action and reaction are equal and opposite (c) If a body is in equilibrium under the action of a number of parallel forces, sum of clockwise moment equals sum of anticlockwise moment (d) If a body is in equilibrium under the action of a number of parallel forces, all forces cancel out
2. What is the dimension for velocity? (a) ML (b) MT (c) L^{-2} (d) LT^{-1}
3. If no net force acts on an object, the object maintains a state of rest or constant speed in a straight line. The above is a statement of Newton's (a) first law of motion (b) second law of motion (c) third law of motion (d) law of universal gravitation
4. A body is projected vertically upward with a speed of 10 ms^{-1} from a point 2m above the ground. Calculate the total time taken for the body to reach the ground. [$g = 10 \text{ ms}^{-1}$]
(a) 0.50 s (b) 1.00 s (c) 2.00 s (d) 3.00 s
5. A force $F = (5i + 3j)\text{N}$ acts on a body and causes a displacement $r = (7i - j)\text{m}$. Determine the work done. (a) 53J (b) 32J (c) 25J (d) 21 J
6. Which of the following is **NOT** simple harmonic motion? (a) The motion of the prongs of a sounding tuning fork (b) The motion of an object suspended from the free end of a spiral spring (c) The motion of the plucked string of a musical instrument (d) The motion of Earth around the sun
7. A mango fruit dropped to the ground from the top of a tree 40 m tall. Find how long it takes the fruit to reach the ground if acceleration due to gravity, $g = 10 \text{ m/s}^2$
(a) 2.82 s (b) 2 s (c) 4 s (d) 80 s
8. A car moving with a velocity of 16 m/s accelerates uniformly at the rate of 1 m/s^2 to reach a velocity of 20 m/s. Find the distance covered (a) 85 m (b) 82 m (c) 75 m (d) 72 m

9. A metre rule is found to balance at the 48 cm mark. When a body of mass 60 g is suspended at the 6 cm mark, the balance point is found to be at the 30 cm mark. Find the mass of the metre rule. (a) 60 g (b) 80 g (c) 92 g (d) 100 g.
10. A car of mass 1000 kg travels with a velocity 45 km/h on a rough road and it is brought to a rest after 10s. What is the force exerted on the car?
(a) 1333 N (b) 1282 N (c) 1250 N (d) 1067 N
11. What is the kinetic energy of a rock of mass 220 g after it has fallen freely for 5 seconds? [$g=10 \text{ m/s}^2$]. (a) 350 J (b) 275 J (c) 250 J (d) 225 J
12. A pile driver of mass 125 kg falls through a height of 80 m before striking the pile. What is its momentum at the instance it strikes the pile? [$g = 10\text{m/s}^2$]
(a) 40 kg.m/s (b) 1600 kg.m/s (c) 5000 kg.m/s (d) 5000 kg.m/s
13. A solid of mass 1 kg suspended by a string, is completely immersed in water. If the tension in the string is 5 N, calculate the upthrust on the solid [Take $g= 9.78 \text{ m/s}^2$]
(a) 4.78 N (b) 8.0 N (c) 9.78N (d) 47 N
14. A car travels with a constant velocity of 45 km/h for 10 s. What is the distance it covers in this time? (a) 450 m (b) 400 m (c) 125 m (d) 45 m
15. How much water at 0°C is needed to cool 0.5 kg of water at 80°C down 20°C ?
(a) 1.5 kg (b) 1.85 kg (c) 2.0 kg (d) 2.5 kg
16. The pressure applied to an enclosed fluid at one end is transmitted equally throughout the fluid and to the container walls. This statement is (a) Archimedes' principle (b) Bernoulli's principle (c) Pascal's principle (d) Heisenberg's uncertainty principle
17. The amount of heat that is required to raise the temperature of unit mass of a substance one degree Celsius is called
(a) Heat capacity (b) thermal capacity (c) Specific heat (d) Heat energy
18. The only mode of heat energy transfer that needs no material medium is
(a) Convection (b) Radiation (c) Conduction (d) Thermal conduction
19. Thermal equilibrium between two objects exist when (a) the heat capacity of both objects are the same (b) one object loses heat continuously to the other (c) temperature of both objects are equal (d) the quantity of heat in both objects is the same.
20. Which of the following statements is **NOT** true of a real image formed by a concave mirror?

- (a) It is inverted (b) It is erect (c) It can be observed on a screen (d) it is amplify
21. A steel bar has a width of 10 cm at 50°C. At what temperature will it fit exactly into a hole of constant width 10.005 cm if coefficient of linear expansion of steel is $11 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}^{-1}$?
- (a) 75.5°C (b) 75° (c) 0.005°C (d) -75.5°C
22. The amount of heat required to produce unit temperature rise in a substance is called.
- (a) Heat capacity (b) Latent heat (c) Specific heat capacity (d) Specific latent heat
23. A bullet of mass 15 g is fired from a riffle with a velocity 100 m/s. If the mass of the riffle is 1 kg. What is the recoil velocity of the riffle?
- (a) 1.2 m/s (b) 1.5 m/s (c) 1.8 m/s (d) 2.1 m/s
24. A body of mass 2 kg moves velocity of 10 m/s. Neglecting air resistance, determine the kinetic energy of the body. (a) 200 N (b) 200 J (c) 100 J (d) 100 N
25. The speed of light in air is 3.0×10^8 m/s. What is its speed in glass having a refractive index of 1.65? (a) 6.0×10^8 m/s (b) 4.95×10^8 m/s (c) 1.82×10^8 m/s (d) 1.65×10^8 m/s
26. A body of mass 2 kg, moving with velocity 5 m/s collides with stationary body of mass 0.5 kg if the two bodies move together after impact, calculate their common velocity.
- (a) 1 m/s^2 (b) 2 m/s^2 (c) 2.5 m/s (d) 4 m/s^2
27. A gun of mass 0.1kg has a bullet of mass 0.1kg , the bullet laves the piston when fired at a velocity of 200m/s , find the final velocity (a) 18 m/s (b) 20 m/s (c) 30 m/s (d) 45 m/s
28. The main evidence that light rays travel in a straight line is that; **I** Incident, reflected and the normal lie in the same plane, **II** Pin-hole camera, **III** eclipse of the sun, **IV** Divergence of light rays. (a) **II** Only (b) **III** only (c) **III&IV** only (d) **I, II, &III** only
29. A swimming pool is 2.1 m deep. If it contains water of refractive index 1.3, calculate the apparent depth of the pool. (a) 1.6 m (b) 1.7 m (c) 1.8 m (d) 1.9 m
30. An object is placed 20 cm from a concave mirror of focal length 15 cm. calculate the linear magnification of the image formed. (a) 0.5 (b) 1.5 (c) 2.0 (d) 3.0

APPENDIX VI

Detailed description of the number of questionnaires and achievement tests administered to the students in each school visited.

S/N	NAME OF SCHOOL	NUMBER OF INSTRUMENTS ADMINISTERED
1	Christ's (Boys) School, Ado-Ekiti	58
2	All Souls Anglican Grammar School, Ado-Ekiti	48
3	Baptist Comprehensive High School, Ado-Ekiti	24
4	Corpus Christi College, Ilawe-Ekiti	52
5	United High School, Ilawe-Ekiti	31
6	Community High School, Igbaraodo Ekiti	17
7	Alarelu Comprehensive High School, Igbaraodo Ekiti	18
8	Ekiti Baptist High School, Igede-Ekiti	38
9	Government Science College, Iyin-Ekiti	62
10	Eyemote Comprehensive High School, Iyin-Ekiti	28
11	Aramoko District Community Secondary School, Aramoko-Ekiti	44
12	Community High School, Aramoko-EKITI	30
TOTAL		450

UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN, IBADAN NIGERIA
INSTITUTE OF EDUCATION

LAUREATE OF THE 2014 ADEA/AFDB
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22 June 2017

Dear Sir/Ma,

LETTER OF INTRODUCTION – APATA Olukayode Emmanuel (MATRIC NO: 196042)

I hereby wish to introduce the bearer who is a Post Graduate Student in the Institute of Education, University of Ibadan. He has been authorized to collect data for his study.

In view of this, I hereby solicit your kind support to accord him necessary assistance.

Thank you.

Yours Faithfully,

22/6/17

Dr. Monica N. Odinko
Head of Unit, ICEE

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▪ Emeritus Professor E. A. Yeloye
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